

COST Action
Mining the European Anthroposphere (MINEA)
Working Group 1: Resource potential of construction and demolition waste

Deliverable 1.1
Recovery technologies
for construction and demolition waste

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EUROPEAN
ANTHROSPHERE**

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Content

List of Figures	iii
List of Tables	iv
Terms and Definitions.....	v
Acronyms.....	ix
1 INTRODUCTION	1
2 CONSTRUCTION AND DEMOLITION WASTE RECYCLING AND RECOVERY TECHNOLOGIES: LITERATURE REVIEW.....	2
3 RECOVERY TECHNOLOGIES FOR CONSTRUCTION AND DEMOLITION WASTE WORKSHOP	3
3.1 Workshop programme.....	3
3.2 Workshop Book of Abstracts	4
4 CURRENT CONSTRUCTION AND DEMOLITION WASTE STATUS IN EUROPE.....	6
4.1 Construction and demolition waste policy framework	6
4.2 Construction and demolition waste generation rates	10
4.2.1 Construction and demolition waste generated in the EU-28 versus turnover, gross domestic product and population	11
4.2.2 Construction and demolition waste generation in EU-28 timeline	15
4.2.3 Construction and demolition waste streams	17
4.3 Construction and demolition waste recovery rates	19
4.4 Performance against EU 2020 construction and demolition waste recovery target.....	24
4.5 Landfilling versus recovery forecast	26
4.6 Construction and demolition waste recovery challenges	28
5 CONSTRUCTION AND DEMOLITION WASTE RECYCLING AND RECOVERY APPROACHES	30
5.1 Construction and demolition waste source collection and separation	30
5.1.1 Particle size separation	31
5.1.2 Material density separation.....	32
5.1.3 Metal separation.....	34
5.1.4 Microwave sensors.....	34
5.1.5 Optic sensor separation	34
5.1.6 X-ray sensors	36
5.2 Construction and demolition waste processing.....	36
5.2.1 Material particle size reduction systems	36
5.2.2 Material volume reduction systems	39
5.3 Construction and demolition waste recovery and treatment.....	39

6	SELECTION RATIONALE FOR CASE STUDIES	40
7	CONSTRUCTION AND DEMOLITION WASTE SORTING TECHNOLOGIES	41
8	CASE STUDIES ON CONSTRUCTION AND DEMOLITION WASTE RECOVERY AND RECYCLING TECHNOLOGIES	46
8.1	Case study 1: concrete, bricks and ceramics waste recycling and recovery technologies.....	46
8.2	Case study 2: gypsum waste recycling and recovery technologies.....	51
8.3	Case study 3: wood waste recycling and recovery technologies.....	54
8.4	Case study 4: asphalt waste recycling and recovery technologies.....	57
8.5	Case study 5: metals waste recycling and recovery technologies.....	60
8.6	Case study 6: asbestos waste recycling and recovery technologies.....	62
9	RECOMMENDATIONS FOR IMPROVING CONSTRUCTION AND DEMOLITION WASTE MANAGEMENT RECOVERY AND RECYCLING	66
	Acknowledgements	67
	References	68

List of Figures

Figure 1. Definition and integration of MINEA working groups (MINEA Cost Action, 2016)	1
Figure 2. Waste hierarchy (European Parliament, 2008).....	6
Figure 3. Waste generated per economic activity (in % over the total generated in the EU for 2014) (Eurostat, 2017)	10
Figure 4. CDW generation and construction turnover for each MS in 2014 (Eurostat, 2017)	13
Figure 5. CDW generation and GDP in PPS for each MS in 2014 (Eurostat, 2017).....	13
Figure 6. CDW generation and per capita for each MS in 2014 (Eurostat, 2017).....	14
Figure 7. CDWE generation per capita from 2004 to 2014 for MS with higher and lower waste generation rates, denoted in red and green respectively.....	16
Figure 8. CDW generation before and after WFD transposition or specific CDW regulation for the EU-28 and high and low MS generating waste (Villoria Sáez and Osmani, 2018)	17
Figure 9. Percentage of each waste stream generated in each MS in 2014 (Eurostat, 2017).....	19
Figure 10. Waste streams generation in the construction sector in 2014 (EU-28) (Eurostat, 2017).....	19
Figure 11. Management of mineral CDW carried out in the EU-28 since 2010 (Eurostat, 2017).....	20
Figure 12. Management of mineral CDW across the MS for 2014 (Eurostat, 2017).....	21
Figure 13. Relation between landfill tax and % of CDW landfilled in 2014 (Villoria Sáez and Osmani, 2018)	22
Figure 14. Relation between landfill tax and % of CDW recovered in 2014 (Villoria Sáez and Osmani, 2018)	22
Figure 15. Amount of CDW recovered and number of waste facilities for each MS in 2014 (Eurostat, 2017)	23
Figure 16. Recovery rates of mineral CDW in EU since 2010 to 2014 (Eurostat, 2017).....	25
Figure 17. Recovery rates of mineral waste from CD in EU in 2014.....	26
Figure 18. Current CDW recovery approaches and associated technologies (Villoria Sáez and Osmani, 2018) ..	30
Figure 19. CDW collection methods	31
Figure 20. CDW collection methods (Revolvy, 2017)	31
Figure 21. Trommel for onsite waste segregation (Ultra Spreader International, 2017)	32
Figure 22. Vibrating screen (Lund Neidel and Bjørn Jakobsen, 2013)	32
Figure 23. Example of Jig sorting (Gundupalli et al., 2017)	33
Figure 24. Example of a common air classifier (Lund Neidel and Bjørn Jakobsen, 2013).....	33
Figure 25. Functional principle of Eddie current separator (Gundupalli et al., 2017)	34
Figure 26. Electromagnetic Spectrum Illustrating SWIR Wavelength Range (Edmund optics, 2017).....	35
Figure 27. Functional principle of NIR sensor-based sorting technology (Vegas et al., 2015).....	35
Figure 28. Functional principle of VIS sorting technology (Japan External Trade Organization, 2013)	36
Figure 29. Example of an onsite shredder (Timberwolf Ltd., 2017)	37
Figure 30. Functional principle of ZenRobotics (Zen Robotics, 2016)	43
Figure 31. Example of a crusher bucket (ANROSS LTD, 2017).....	46
Figure 32. On-site wet classification technology for CBC waste (Mlinar, 2016).....	47
Figure 33. Dry milling technologies used in LIFE CERAM project (Quereda Vázquez et al., 2016)	49
Figure 34. Granulation technologies used in LIFE CERAM project (Quereda Vázquez et al., 2016)	49
Figure 35. Inputs, output and gypsum recycling XL unit (Gypsum Recycling International, 2005)	52
Figure 36. Example of front milling machine (left) and HIR train REMIXER 4500 (right) (WIRTGEN, 2017)	57
Figure 37. Example of CIR recycling train. (County Government, 2017)	58
Figure 38. Example of FDR recycling train (CNCA, 2017).....	59
Figure 39. Summary of CDW recovery and recycling technologies and outputs for each case study	65

List of Tables

Table 1. Recovery technologies for CDW: Content of Workshop Book of Abstracts	5
Table 2. Transposition of the WFD into national regulations for high and low MS generating CDW (EUR-Lex, 2017)	7
Table 3. Landfill bans and taxes for high and low MS generating CDW (Fischer et al., 2012)	9
Table 4. Amount of CDW generation including and excluding materials from excavations for each MS and for the whole EU-28 in 2014 (Eurostat, 2017).....	11
Table 5. Amount of CDW in relation to construction turnover, GDP and population of each MS and for the whole EU-28 during 2014 (Eurostat, 2017).....	12
Table 6. MS ranking with respect to the amount of CDW generated per parameter analysed	15
Table 7. MS with the highest and lowest CDW generation rates	15
Table 8. CDWE generation (kg per capita) and the year of WFD transposition or CDW regulation for high and low MS generating CDW as well as for the EU-28 MS	16
Table 9. CDW landfill versus recovery forecast of two different scenarios for high and low MS generating CDW, based on data from Hogg et al. (2015).	27
Table 11. Synthesis of CDW waste sorting technologies and case studies.....	43
Table 12. Synthesis of waste recycling and recovery technologies for case study 1 (CBC).....	49
Table 13. Synthesis of waste recycling and recovery technologies for case study 2 (G).....	53
Table 14. Synthesis of waste recycling and recovery technologies for case study 3 (W)	56
Table 15. Synthesis of waste recycling and recovery technologies - case study 4 (AP).....	59
Table 16. Synthesis of waste recycling and recovery technologies - case study 5 (M)	61
Table 17. Synthesis of waste recycling and recovery technologies for case study 6 (AB).....	63
Table 18. Recommendations for improving CDW recovery and recycling.....	66

Terms and Definitions

Backfilling: “any recovery operation where suitable waste is used for reclamation purposes in excavated areas or for engineering purposes in landscaping or construction instead of other non-waste materials which would otherwise have been used for that purpose”. (European Commission, 2015)

By-product: “A substance or object, resulting from a production process, the primary aim of which is not the production of that item may be regarded as not being waste referred to in point (1) of Article 3 but as being a by-product only if the following conditions are met: (a) further use of the substance or object is certain; (b) the substance or object can be used directly without any further processing other than normal industrial practice; (c) the substance or object is produced as an integral part of a production process; and (d) further use is lawful, i.e. the substance or object fulfils all relevant product, environmental and health protection requirements for the specific use and will not lead to overall adverse environmental or human health impacts.” (European Parliament, 2008)

Case study: each construction and demolition waste stream analysed in this report.

Construction and Demolition waste (CDW): “any waste generated in the activities of companies belonging to the construction, renovation and demolition sector and included in category 17 of the European List of Wastes from the Commission Decision 2000/532/EC. The category 17 provides for codes for several individual materials that can be collected separately from a construction or demolition site. It includes waste streams [hazardous and non-hazardous; inert, organic and inorganic] resulting from construction, renovation and demolition activities. CDW originates at sites where construction, renovation or demolition takes place. Construction waste contains several materials, often related to cut-offs or packaging waste. Demolition waste comprises all materials found in constructions. Renovation waste can contain both construction-related materials and demolition-related materials”. (European Commission, 2016)

Collection of waste: “gathering of waste, including the preliminary sorting and preliminary storage of waste for the purposes of transport to a waste treatment facility”. (European Parliament, 2008)

Disposal: “any operation which is not recovery even where the operation has as a secondary consequence the reclamation of substances or energy”. (European Parliament, 2008)

Hazardous waste: “waste which displays one or more of the hazardous properties listed in Annex III” of the WFD (European Parliament, 2008).

Inert waste: *“waste that does not undergo any significant physical, chemical or biological transformations. Inert waste will not dissolve burn or otherwise react physically or chemically, biodegrade or adversely affect other matter with which it comes into contact in a way likely to give rise to environmental pollution or harm human health”*. (European Parliament, 1999)

Landfill: *“a waste disposal site for the deposit of the waste onto or into land (for instance underground), including: internal waste disposal sites (for instance own waste disposal carried out by the producer of waste at the place of production), and a permanent site (older than one year) which is used for temporary storage of waste; but excluding:*

- facilities where waste is unloaded in order to permit its preparation for further transport for recovery, treatment or disposal elsewhere;
- storage of waste prior to recovery or treatment for a period less than 3 years as a general rule; and
- *storage of waste prior to disposal for a period less than 1 year”*. (European Parliament, 1999).

Mineral waste from construction and demolition: *“waste originated during construction and demolition activities and considers: concrete, bricks, and gypsum waste; insulation materials; mixed construction wastes containing glass, plastics and wood; and waste hydrocarbonised road-surfacing material. They are hazardous when containing organic pollutants”* (Eurostat, 2010)

Mixed construction and demolition waste: mix of different CDW streams.

Open loop recycling: is the conversion of waste into a new product, in which the inherent properties of the recycled material differ from those of the virgin material. (Huysman et al., 2015)

Prevention: *“measures taken before a substance, material or product has become waste, that reduce: the quantity of waste, including through the re-use of products or the extension of the life span of products; the adverse impacts of the generated waste on the environment and human health; or the content of harmful substances in materials and products”*. (European Parliament, 2008)

Preparing for re-use: *“checking, cleaning or repairing recovery operations, by which products or components of products that have become waste are prepared so that they can be re-used without any other pre-processing”* (European Parliament, 2008)

Re-use: *“any operation by which products or components that are not waste are used again for the same purpose for which they were conceived”*. (European Parliament, 2008)

Recycling: *“any recovery operation by which waste materials are reprocessed into products, materials or substances whether for the original or other purposes. It includes the reprocessing of organic material but does not include energy recovery and the reprocessing into materials that are to be used as fuels or for backfilling operations”*. (European Parliament, 2008)

Recovery: *“any operation the principal result of which is waste serving a useful purpose by replacing other materials which would otherwise have been used to fulfil a*

Renovation: *“work that involves the structural alteration of buildings, the substantial replacement of main services or finishes and/or the substantial changed use of floor space whilst at the same time including associated redecoration and repair works on the one hand and related new building on the other. Renovation covers all the work done to existing buildings as the four R's: renovation, rehabilitation, restoration and remodelling. Renovation is addressed from a broad perspective, including residential, historical and commercial buildings owned and managed by private/public companies or authorities”*. (European Commission, 2016)

Selective demolition: *“involves sequencing the demolition activities to allow the separation and sorting of building materials”*. (European Commission, 2016)

Separate collection: *“where a waste stream is kept separately by type and nature so as to facilitate a specific treatment”*. (European Parliament, 2008)

Sorting: separation of waste streams from mixed CDW.

Treatment: *“recovery or disposal operations, including preparation prior to recovery or disposal”* (European Parliament, 2008)

Waste: *“any substance or object which the holder discards or intends or is required to discard”* (European Parliament, 2008)

Waste holder: *“the waste producer or the natural or legal person who is in possession of the waste”*. (European Parliament, 2008)

Waste management: *“the collection, transport, recovery and disposal of waste, including the supervision of such operations and the after-care of disposal sites, and including actions taken as a dealer or broker”*. (European Parliament, 2008)

Waste management plan (WMP): *“set out an analysis of the current waste management situation in the geographical entity concerned, as well as the measures to be taken with respect to environmentally sound preparation for re-use, recycling, recovery and disposal of waste and*

an evaluation of how the plan will support the implementation of the objectives and provisions of the WFD” (European Commission, 2013)

Waste minimization: *“action to prevent waste being produced in order to minimise or reduce the amount of waste requiring final disposal” (European Commission, 2012)*

Waste producer: *“anyone whose activities produce waste (original waste producer) or anyone who carries out pre-processing, mixing or other operations resulting in a change in the nature or composition of this waste” (European Parliament, 2008)*

Acronyms

AB – Asbestos

ADR – Advanced Dry Recovery

AP – Asphalt

BF – Blast Furnace

BOF – Basic Oxygen Furnace

CBC - Concrete, bricks and ceramics

CD – Construction and demolition

CDW – Construction and demolition waste

CDWE – Construction and demolition waste including excavation

CIR - In-place cold recycling

CCPR - Central-plant cold recycling

CT – Construction turnover

DE-XRT - Dual Energy X-ray Transmission

EAF – Electric Arc Furnace

ELW - European List of Waste classification

EU – Europe

EWC-STAT - European Waste Catalogue classification

FDR - Full Depth Reclamation

G – Gypsum

HIR - Hot in-place recycling

HIS - Hyperspectral imaging

HPR - Hot plant recycling

LIBS - Laser Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy

LRR – Literature Review Report

M – Metals

MFA – Material Flow analysis

MS – Member States

NIR - Near infrared

NP – Number of population

PPS – Purchasing power standards

PRM – Primary Raw Materials

SWI - Short-wave Infrared

SRM – Secondary Raw Materials

VIS - Visual spectrometry

W – Wood

WBoA – MINEA Workshop on recovery technologies for CDW recycling Book of Abstracts

WFD – Waste Framework Directive

WG – Working Group

XRF - X-ray Fluorescence

1 INTRODUCTION

This report addresses Deliverable 1.1 “Resource potential of construction and demolition waste (CDW)” developed by Working Group 1 “Resource potential of construction and demolition waste (CDW)” of the COST Action MINEA project (Mining the European Anthroposphere). MINEA aims to quantify and assess the material resources and reserves in the Anthroposphere and consolidate existing knowledge related to the exploration, evaluation and classification of materials in anthropogenic deposits and waste flows.

The structure of MINEA COST Action comprises five working groups (WG) (Figure 1):

- WG1: Resource potential of CDW
- WG2: Resource potential of waste in landfills
- WG3: Resource potential of solid residues from waste incineration
- WG4: Classification and reporting of material resources/reserves
- WG5: Knowledge management & dissemination

COST Action “Mining the European Anthroposphere”

Figure 1. Definition and integration of MINEA working groups (MINEA Cost Action, 2016)

This report integrates the activities carried out in Working Group 1 (WG1) of the MINEA project. The following documents were developed from the activities undertaken by WG1: (1) Literature Review Report and (2) MINEA WG1 Workshop on CDW recovery technologies, which culminate in recommendations to address the current challenges to the circularity of secondary construction materials.

Both activities examine current practices, knowledge-technologies transfer and CDW recycling and recovery advances across European regions. This information is critical to attaining high-quality secondary materials and enhancing circular economy uptake in the construction sector.

2 CONSTRUCTION AND DEMOLITION WASTE RECYCLING AND RECOVERY TECHNOLOGIES: LITERATURE REVIEW

The Literature Review Report appraises the current situation regarding CDW generation trends, recovery rates and challenges across the European Union and identifies existing and emerging CDW recovery technologies for six key waste streams (case studies): concrete, bricks & ceramics (CBC), gypsum (G), wood (W), asphalt (AP), metal (M), and asbestos (AB), including methods and tools for their sorting, processing, recycling and recovering. Finally, the main findings are analysed and discussed in order to generate recommendations to address blockers to CDW recycling and recovery.

This report contributes to existing knowledge through the categorization of current and emerging recovery technologies in relation to the key CDW waste streams, through assessment of their limitations and by offering recommendations to address existing barriers.

The Literature Review Report is addressed in chapters 4 to 9 of this report.

- **Chapter 4** gives an overview of the situation of CDW in Europe in terms of generation, recovery and performance against the 2020 target in order to identify the main challenges to be addressed by relevant stakeholders. For this, the most recent data published by Eurostat statistics (2010) were used.
- **Chapter 5** outlines CDW recycling and recovery approaches.
- **Chapter 6** examines the case studies that are analysed in this report.
- **Chapters 7 and 8** assess the existing and emerging CDW recovery technologies, including methods and tools for sorting, processing, recycling and recovering of the case studies.
- **Chapter 9** forwards recommendations on CDW recovery improvement.

3 RECOVERY TECHNOLOGIES FOR CONSTRUCTION AND DEMOLITION WASTE WORKSHOP

WG1 Workshop “Recovery technologies for CDW” was held in the Technische Universität Wien (Vienna) on 16-17 of November 2016. The WG1 Workshop aimed to give a comprehensive overview of innovative recovery and recycling technologies for CDW flows in buildings and infrastructure across European regions.

3.1 Workshop programme

The workshop programme included several keynote and plenary talks and oral presentations and specialised debate sessions¹ (MINEA Cost Action, 2016).

Day 1: Wednesday 16th November 2016

09:00	REGISTRATION
09:30	OPENING AND INTRODUCTION
09:30	Welcome and workshop overview Mohamed Osmani (Loughborough University, UK)
09:40	COST Action CA15115: Mining the European Anthroposphere (MINEA) Ulrich Kral (TU Wien, Austria)
10:00	KEYNOTE PRESENTATIONS
10:00	ZenRobotics waste sorting technologies Maciej Borkowski (ZenRobotics, Finland)
10:30	Material Flow Analysis of stocks and flows to assess construction and demolition waste recovery potential Clemens Deilmann (Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban & Regional Development, Germany)
11:00	Strategies for the recovery and recycling of raw materials from construction and demolition waste: IRCOW and HISER projects Amaia Lisbona (Tecnalia, Spain)
11:30	COFFEE BREAK
11:45	Construction and demolition waste recovery assessment and optimisation Mohamed Osmani (Loughborough University, UK)
12:15	Recycling and closing the loop for gypsum products: The European Gypsum Industry circular economy approach Christine Marlet (Eurogypsum, Belgium)
12:45	Recycling of construction finishing work wastes Rym Mtibaa (Recylum, France)
13:15	LUNCH
14:00	BREAKOUT SESSION
	Topic 1: Construction and demolition waste recovery challenges. Topic 2: Construction and demolition waste recovery enablers. Session facilitator: Mohamed Osmani (Loughborough University, UK).
15:30	COFFEE BREAK
15:45	DEBATE

¹ WG1 Workshop abstracts, presentations and biographies are available at: <http://www.minea-network.eu/event.php?id=3>

	The EC and Member States' actions and incentives to support the industry to achieve the Waste Framework Directive target to reuse, recycle and recover 70% (by weight) of construction and demolition waste by 2020.
	Panel members: Maciej Borkowski (ZenRobotics, Finland); Clemens Deilmann (Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development, Germany); Amaia Lisbona (Tecnalia, Spain); Christine Marlet (Eurogypsum, Belgium); Rym Mtibaa (Recylum, France).
17:00	CLOSE OF DAY 1 ACTIVITIES

Day 2: Thursday 17th November 2016

09:00	WELCOME AND DAY 2 PROGRAMME
	Overview of Day 2 workshop activities Mohamed Osmani (Loughborough University, UK)
09:10	PLENARY PRESENTATION
	On-site wet-screening of construction and demolition waste. Christian Mlinar (Bernegger GmbH, Austria).
9:40	SESSION 1: CONSTRUCTION AND DEMOLITION WASTE RECOVERY - NATIONAL AND REGIONAL STRATEGIES
09:40	New initiatives in Belgium to improve current construction and demolition waste management practice and to develop innovative solutions. Jeroen Vrijders (Belgian Building Research Institute, Belgium)
10:10	Construction and demolition waste management and recovery in Lombardy Region, Italy. Lucia Rigamonti (Politecnico di Milano, Italy)
10:40	COFFEE BREAK
11:00	SESSION 2: CONSTRUCTION AND DEMOLITION WASTE RECOVERY TOOLS
11:00	Clean-Way software facilitating construction and demolition waste recycling- real-time data to reach zero waste. Krisztián Petrovski (Clean-Way Ltd, Hungary)
11:30	Dynamic Performance Assessment of construction and demolition waste recovery policies. Ibrahim Motawa (Heriot-Watt University, Scotland).
12:00	Density-based separation of heterogeneous construction and demolition waste mixtures Erik Marklund (Luleå University of Technology, Sweden)
12:30	WORKSHOP CLOSING REMARKS AND COST Action CA15115 (MINEA) - NEXT STAGES
	Mohamed Osmani (Loughborough University, UK) and Ulrich Kral (TU Wien, Austria)
13:00	LUNCH

3.2 Workshop Book of Abstracts

A Workshop Book of Abstracts (WBoA) was produced that includes the workshop's scope, agenda, abstracts and biographies of presenters. The WBoA as well as the oral presentations are available online² (MINEA Cost Action, 2016). A total of 14 abstracts by researchers and industry practitioners, research centres and industrial companies were compiled into the WBoA (Table 1), which encompasses: three tools, six methodologies/projects, and five technologies/practices for CDW recovery and recycling (MINEA Cost Action, 2016).

² WG1 Workshop abstracts are available at: <http://www.minea-network.eu/event.php?id=3>

Table 1. Recovery technologies for CDW: Content of Workshop Book of Abstracts

	Title	Description	Presenter	Country
TECHNOLOGIES	ZenRobotics waste sorting technologies	Presented an intelligent robotic waste sorting system	Borkowsky, M	Finland
	Strategies for the recovery and recycling of raw materials from CDW: IRCOW and HISER projects	Presented the results of IRCOW and HISER projects. Both projects aimed to adapt advanced sorting technologies, i.e. including electro-fragmentation, ADR classification/refining process and LIBS-based quality assurance system.	Lisbona, A	Spain
	Recycling and closing the loop for gypsum products: European Gypsum Industry circular economy approach	Presented GtoG project results. Among the results obtained, they proved that it is feasible to incorporate (up to 30% of) recycled gypsum in Type A plasterboard manufacturing.	Marlet, C	Belgium
	Density based separation of heterogeneous CDW mixtures	Presented a new tool for recovering waste with an organic content too low for incineration and yet too high for landfilling. The tool is based on density separation using water. Up to 40% of the organic carbon was separated from the material, and the resulting sink fraction can be accepted at class II landfills.	Marklund, E	Finland
	On-site Wet-Screening of CDW	Presented a portable-container for CDW treatment based on a multi-stage wet screening process. The process water is circulated and continuously processed in the plant itself.	Mlinar, C	Austria
METHODS	Construction and demolition waste recovery assessment and optimisation	Presented the PEERA method, which is a waste mapping and decision support tool to explore CDW recycling potential opportunities.	Osmani, M	United Kingdom
	Improving the recovery of CDW	Presented the results of DEMOCLES project. The technical and economic difficulties of selective demolition were identified and a common framework and recommendations for selective deconstruction were defined.	Mtibaa, R Grimaud, H	France
	Construction and Demolition Waste Management and Recovery in Lombardy Region, Italy	Presented a method to evaluate the environmental performance of the CDW recovery chain in Lombardy Region by applying the Life Cycle Assessment method.	Rigamonti, L Pantini, S	Italy
	Dynamic Performance Assessment of the Construction and demolition waste recovery policies	Presented a System Dynamics (SD) model to analyse profiles of CDW recovery considering the interrelationships among the influential variables (i.e. technology, economics and climate)	Motawa, I	United Kingdom
TOOLS	New initiatives in Belgium to improve current CDW management practice and to develop innovative solutions	Presented Tracimat, a tool aimed to control and regulate the demolition works.	Vrijders, J	Belgium
	Clean-Way software facilitating CDW recycling - real-time data to reach Zero waste goal	Presented the ICT tool, a software aimed to help every stakeholder of the construction industry: municipalities, constructors and waste recyclers by collecting and showing real-time data of CDW management.	Petrovszki, K	Hungary
	Material Flow Analysis of stocks & flows to assess construction & demolition waste recovery potential	Presented a tool based on Material flow analysis (MFA) aiming to promote the circular economy and considering both quantitative and qualitative aspects of in- and outflows.	Deilmann, C	Germany

4 CURRENT CONSTRUCTION AND DEMOLITION WASTE STATUS IN EUROPE

This section examines the current CDW status in Europe in terms of:

- CDW policy framework;
- CDW generation rates;
- CDW recovery rates;
- Performance against EU 2020 CDW recovery target;
- Landfilling versus recovery forecast; and
- CDW recovery challenges.

4.1 Construction and demolition waste policy framework

In 2008 the European Commission approved the Waste Framework Directive 2008/98/EC (WFD), providing a general framework of waste management (WM) requirements and setting definitions regarding waste for the whole European Union (European Parliament, 2008). This Directive also introduces a detailed clarification of the waste hierarchy, which makes prevention the top WM priority, followed by reusing, recycling or other forms of valorisation and, finally, landfill/deposit (Figure 2). The WFD also requires that all MS ensure that their competent authorities establish one or more Waste Management Plans (WMP) covering their entire geographical territory. These WMP should review the current WM situation (the type, quantity and source of waste generated, including information on CDWs) and document the measures that will be taken to improve waste management in line with the waste hierarchy (European Commission, 2011, Justice and Environment, 2012).

Figure 2. Waste hierarchy (European Parliament, 2008)

One of the objectives of the WFD is to provide a framework for moving towards a European recycling society with a high level of resource efficiency. In particular, the Directive sets a quantitative target for CDW which has to be achieved by 2020: *"MS shall take the necessary measures designed to achieve that by 2020 a minimum of 70% (by weight) of non-hazardous*

CDW excluding naturally occurring material defined in category 170504 in the List of Wastes³ shall be prepared for re-use, recycled or undergo other material recovery". MS are required to transpose the WFD into their national policies before 2012. Table 2 shows the policies and regulations regarding CDW management developed in MS based on the severity of CDW generation, which is further discussed at the end of section 4.2.1 (see Table 7).

Table 2. Transposition of the WFD into national regulations for high and low MS generating CDW (EUR-Lex, 2017)

	MS	National Regulation	Specific for CDW*
MS with the highest CDW generation	Austria	Federal Act amending the Waste Management Act 2002 (AWG amendment 2010)	-
	Belgium	Legislation of CDW varies from one region to another (three different waste legislations). Brussels Capital Region transposed European Directive in 2012.	-
	France	Law 2009-967 of 3 August 2009 and Law 2010-788 of 12 July 2010 make pre-audits compulsory on demolition sites and departmental CDW management plans.	✓
	Germany	The Circular Economy Act (KrWG) is currently the main waste disposal regulation. The legal framework for CDW recycling is specified in different state laws.	-
	Italy	D.Lgs 152/2006 is the main piece of legislation on waste.	-
	Netherlands	Act of 3 February 2011 amending the Environmental Management Act, the Environmental Taxes Act and the Economic Offences Act for the implementation of Directive no. 2008/98 / EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of the European Union.	-
MS with the lowest CDW	Croatia	The Act on Sustainable Waste Management (OG 94/13)	-
	Portugal	Decree-Law 46/2008 establishes the legal framework for waste management resulting from construction works or demolition of buildings or collapses.	✓
	Slovakia	Act no. 343/2012 Coll., Amending Act no. 223/2001 Coll. on Waste and on the Modification and Supplementation of Certain Acts, as amended, and on amendments to certain laws.	-
	Slovenia	Decree on the management of waste arising from construction work of 22 April 2008.	✓
	Spain	National Law for CDW management - Royal Decree 105/2008	✓
	Poland	Act on Waste of 2012	-

* MS with specific national regulation for CDW management

Despite the fact that all MS have transposed the WFD into their national regulations, just four MS (France, Portugal, Slovenia and Spain) have developed specific regulations for CDW management, while other MS developed Waste Management Plans or regulations pertaining to local authorities. For instance, Flanders (Belgium) has implemented a plan of execution for CDW since 1995 and Germany started a voluntary commitment to halve the amount of CDW landfilled in 1996 (Deloitte, 2016, Monier et al., 2011). Among the MS with the highest CDW generation, France is the only EU country with a national regulation for CDW management,

³ The List of Wastes is published in the Commission Decision 2000/532/EC. EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT 2000. Commission Decision of 3 May 2000 replacing Decision 94/3/EC establishing a list of wastes pursuant to Article 1(a) of Council Directive 75/442/EEC on waste and Council Decision 94/904/EC establishing a list of hazardous waste pursuant to Article 1(4) of Council Directive 91/689/EEC on hazardous waste (notified under document number C(2000) 1147).

but this considers only demolition activities. By contrast, half of the MS generating less CDW have a specific national regulation for CDW management.

In addition to the WFD, several MS have implemented landfill taxes or bans to reduce the amount of CDW generated and to improve its management. Landfill taxes have been implemented differently in different MS, with some countries having regional disparities or variations for different materials. For example, the Netherlands has a landfill ban on recyclables and Belgium has bans in mixed CDW landfill (CEWEP, 2017). Denmark has a ban on landfilling of waste suitable for incineration, which would explain the low levels of landfilling and relatively high levels of CDW incineration (5%).

According to the last report published by the European Environment Agency (EEA), 24 of the 28 EU MS use landfill taxes as part of their waste management policies (EEA, 2016). Landfill taxation coverage and rates vary among the different MS, ranging from 3€/t in Lithuania to more than 100€/t in Belgium (CEWEP, 2017). The remaining 4 MS without landfill taxation are: Cyprus, Germany, Luxemburg and Malta. Moreover, Greece recently suspended the landfill tax in 2017 and Croatia is encouraging the implementation of a landfill tax in its WMP, but has not applied it yet (CEWEP, 2017).

Table 3 summarizes the landfill taxes of the highest and lowest CDW MS (see Table 7). Landfill taxes vary considerably among MS in terms of both quantity and type of waste streams, making it thus difficult to correlate landfill tax to CDW generation.

Table 3. Landfill bans and taxes for high and low MS generating CDW (Fischer et al., 2012)

MS	B ^a	T ^a	Details	Tax for CDW €/tonne	Source	
High MS generating CDW	Austria	✓	✓	Tax exists since 1999. For MSW is around 87€/t but depends on composition of waste and standard of the landfill. For construction or inert waste and soil excavation: 9.20 €/t	9.20	(Ettlinger and Bapasola, 2016)
	Belgium	✓	✓	Brussels has no landfills. Flanders has a landfill tax which ranges from 56.05 €/t for non-combustible waste to 101.91 €/t for combustible waste Wallonia ranges from 62.16 €/t for non-combustible waste to 113.01 €/t for general waste	56.05-113.01	(CEWEP, 2017)
	France	✓	✓	Vary from 150€/t to 15 €/t depending on the standard of the landfill and not on the nature of waste streams. The general landfill tax (2014): 30€/t and (2015): 40€/t	30.00	(CEWEP, 2017)
	Germany	✓	✗	No tax	-	(CEWEP, 2017)
	Italy	✗	✓	Vary between the different regions (2008 to 2012): Inert waste: EUR 1.03-10.33 €/t Hazardous and non-hazardous waste including MSW: 5.16-25.82 €/t	1.03-10.33	(CEWEP, 2017)
	Netherlands	✓	✓	Introduced in 1995, repealed in 2012 and reintroduced in 2015. 13.11 € per tonne in 2017	13.11	(Deloitte, 2015b) (CEWEP, 2017)
	Croatia	✓	✗	No tax. A fee is encouraged by the WMP for 2017-2022, but not applied yet.	-	(CEWEP, 2017)
Low MS generating CDW	Poland	✓	✓	33 €/t (140 PLN) in 2018; 40 €/t (170 PLN) in 2019; 40 €/t (270 PLN) from 2020	33.00	(CEWEP, 2017)
	Portugal	✗	✓	Tax introduced in 2007. 4.27 €/tonne (CDW) in 2014	4.27	(Marinheiro and Russo, 2014)
	Slovakia	✓	✓	Tax introduced in 2014 and rates vary since 2016 depending on the number of separated fractions: MSW: 9.96 €/t (less than 4 separate fractions) to 4.98 €/t (in 5 separate fractions) Hazardous waste: 33.19 €/t Inert waste: 0.33 €/t Other waste 6.64 €/t Biowaste 13.28 €/t	0.33	(CEWEP, 2017)
	Slovenia	✓	✓	Tax introduced in 2001. (still in application in 2017) MSW/Non-hazardous waste: 11€/t Inert: 2.2 €/t Hazardous: 22 €/t	2.2	(CEWEP, 2017)
	Spain	✗	✓	Landfill taxes vary in each region: MSW: 12-30 €/t. Will reach 41.3 €/t in 2019. Industrial waste: 2-35€/t CDW: 0,5- 4€/t	0,5- 4	(CEWEP, 2017)

4.2 Construction and demolition waste generation rates

According to the latest Eurostat statistics (Eurostat, 2017), the EU construction and demolition (CD) sector was the highest waste producer among all economic activities, accounting for 35% of the total generated, which amounts to more than four times the total household waste produced in the EU (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Waste generated per economic activity (in % over the total generated in the EU for 2014) (Eurostat, 2017)

The CD sector in EU-28 generated around 858 Mtonnes in 2014 of CDW and excavations (CDWE), including 522 Mtonnes of soil and dredging spoil (Eurostat, 2017). Thus, 336 Mtonnes of CDW (excluding excavations) were generated in the EU in 2014 (Eurostat, 2017). Table 4 shows the amount of CDW reported by the EU MS to Eurostat for the year 2014, distinguishing the amount of waste materials from excavations (Eurostat, 2017). As shown in Table 4, larger countries generate greater amounts of CDW. For this reason, the amount of waste generated cannot be considered as a single parameter to quantify the waste generation rate. Other factors such as construction turnover, Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in terms of purchasing power standards (PPS)⁴, and the per capita of each MS need to be also considered.

⁴ "GDP in PPS eliminates differences in price levels between countries, and calculations on a per capita basis allow for the comparison of economies significantly different in absolute size" Eurostat (2017)

Table 4. Amount of CDW generation including and excluding materials from excavations for each MS and for the whole EU-28 in 2014 (Eurostat, 2017)

MS	Tonnes of CDWE (incl. soils and dredging spoils)	Tonnes of soil	Tonnes of dredging spoil	Tonnes of CDW (excl. soil or dredging spoils)
Austria	40265570	30496258	:	9769312
Belgium	17077950	1071336	34796	15971818
Bulgaria	1340467	137289	673732	529446
Croatia	618158	262362	3149	352647
Cyprus	634801	474423	60	160318
Czech Republic	9409944	6910944	45377	2453623
Denmark	10572098	6367518	86	4204494
Estonia	671347	283859	28826	358662
EU-28	858750000	442420000	79600000	336730000
Finland	16296811	14924200	:	1372611
France	227607180	153676916	1817006	72113258
Germany	206466169	114485384	1007903	90972882
Greece	479999	:	:	479999
Hungary	3439941	1289331	16113	2134497
Ireland	1884390	1681897	3	202490
Italy	51683579	11712710	32585	39938284
Latvia	454281	:	:	454281
Lithuania	434737	4525	:	430212
Luxembourg	5979235	5405201	:	574034
Malta	1241079	:	216909	1024170
Netherlands	90734851	5644309	61307656	23782886
Poland	17010251	12042355	690848	4277048
Portugal	1512950	583826	2424	926700
Romania	1050434	603101	26	447307
Slovakia	1386685	276514	763350	346821
Slovenia	815010	445311	250488	119211
Spain	20418071	14766709	:	5651362
Sweden	8866720	5400000	1200000	2266720
United Kingdom	120393877	53471660	11504018	55418199

: No available data

4.2.1 Construction and demolition waste generated in the EU-28 versus turnover, gross domestic product and population

Table 5 summarizes the data for the three parameters analysed, as well as for the total amount of CDW generated in CD activities in EU-28 MS in 2014. Values surpassing the mean value for the EU-28 have been marked in red, while the five lowest values are shown in green.

Table 5. Amount of CDW in relation to construction turnover, GDP and population of each MS and for the whole EU-28 during 2014 (Eurostat, 2017)

MS	CDW (Mtonnes)	Parameters analysed			Tonnes of CDW per parameter		
		Turnover (M€)	GDP (PPS)	Capita (x10 ⁶)	t/M€ of turnover	t/GDP	t/ per capita
Austria	9.77	43341.60	307338.40	8.51	225.40	31.79	1.15
Belgium	15.97	62065.00	368199.60	11.20	257.34	43.38	1.43
Bulgaria	0.53	7924.50	92242.20	7.25	66.81	5.74	0.07
Croatia	0.35	5062.40	69001.80	4.25	69.66	5.11	0.08
Cyprus	0.16	1789.40	19105.20	0.86	89.59	8.39	0.19
Czech Republic	2.45	25390.50	250064.60	10.40	96.64	9.81	0.24
Denmark	4.20	28316.20	198482.30	5.62	148.48	21.18	0.75
Estonia	0.36	3910.30	27561.00	1.32	91.72	13.01	0.27
EU-28	336.73	1577430.10	14043716.60	507.37	213.47	23.98	0.66
Finland	1.37	28998.40	166464.70	5.45	47.33	8.25	0.25
France	72.11	288852.70	1958925.30	66.08	249.65	36.81	1.09
Germany	90.97	241201.40	2806272.00	80.70	377.17	32.42	1.13
Greece	0.48	11081.60	212233.00	10.99	43.31	2.26	0.04
Hungary	2.13	13044.00	185781.90	9.88	163.64	11.49	0.22
Ireland	0.20	14208.20	175037.90	4.60	14.25	1.16	0.04
Italy	39.94	170611.60	1619948.10	61.15	234.09	24.65	0.65
Latvia	0.45	4177.20	35042.40	2.00	108.75	12.96	0.23
Lithuania	0.43	4920.40	60582.00	2.94	87.43	7.10	0.15
Luxembourg	0.57	6887.90	41613.60	0.55	83.34	13.79	1.04
Malta	1.02	947.70	10641.10	0.43	1080.69	96.25	2.41
Netherlands	23.78	79287.00	606916.80	17.08	299.96	39.19	1.39
Poland	4.28	59925.20	717518.10	38.02	71.37	5.96	0.11
Portugal	0.93	18134.40	219990.20	10.43	51.10	4.21	0.09
Romania	0.45	15365.40	303741.70	19.94	29.11	1.47	0.02
Slovakia	0.35	8030.80	115674.10	5.40	43.19	3.00	0.06
Slovenia	0.12	4787.60	47280.80	2.06	24.90	2.52	0.06
Spain	5.65	98546.20	1149572.20	46.51	57.35	4.92	0.12
Sweden	2.27	63272.70	330368.80	9.64	35.82	6.86	0.24
United Kingdom	55.42	268299.10	1946764.10	64.11	206.55	28.47	0.86

* Values surpassing the mean value for the EU-28 have been marked in red, while the 5 lowest values were marked in green.

The following sections and figures analyse the data shown in Table 5, comparing the amount of CDW generated and the construction turnover, GDP and per capita for each MS.

- CDW generation and construction turnover** for each MS in 2014 is shown in Figure 4. For example, the amount of CDW generated by Germany and the Netherlands (denoted with a red dot) exceeds the amount of construction turnover of the MS (denoted with vertical column bar). By contrast, there are many other countries performing better in terms of CDW generation relative to construction turnover, such as, for example, Spain, Sweden and Poland, with an amount of CDW generation below their construction turnover.

Moreover, considering the amount of CDW generated per M€ of turnover, the EU-28 MS generated on average around 213.47 tonnes per M€ of turnover in 2014 (Table 5). In particular, seven MS surpassed the EU-28 average, but Germany, the Netherlands and Malta can be highlighted as they produced significantly more, surpassing 250 tonnes/M€ of turnover. By contrast, Romania, Slovenia and Ireland produced very small amounts, not even reaching 20 tonnes/M€ of turnover.

Figure 4. CDW generation and construction turnover for each MS in 2014 (Eurostat, 2017)

- Relationships between **CDW generation and GDP** for each MS in 2014 are shown in Figure 5. The data reveals that countries such as France, the Netherlands and Belgium generated more waste in correlation to their GDP, while others such as Spain, Romania, Poland or Portugal generated well below relative to their GDP. Moreover, considering the amount of CDW generated per GDP (Table 5), the average for the EU-28 is 23.98 tonnes per GDP in PPS for the year 2014. Eight MS (Malta, Belgium, the Netherlands, France, Germany, Austria, United Kingdom and Italy) surpassed this average.

Figure 5. CDW generation and GDP in PPS for each MS in 2014 (Eurostat, 2017)

- Relationships between **CDW generation and population** for each MS in 2014 are shown in Figure 6. Data reveals that countries such as the Netherlands and Belgium have higher rates of CDW generation per capita than other countries such as Spain, Romania, Poland or Portugal, which generate lower CDW, not reaching 0.1 t/per capita. The EU-28 MS generated on average around 0.66 t/per capita in 2014 (Table 5).

Figure 6. CDW generation and per capita for each MS in 2014 (Eurostat, 2017)

Finally, Table 6 shows the MS ranking in terms CDW generation severity, taking the three parameters analysed (turnover, GDP and population) into consideration. It is evident that Malta, Germany, Netherlands, Belgium, Austria and France are among the highest CDW generators above the EU average, while countries producing the lowest amount of CDW in the three parameters analysed include Slovenia, Slovakia, Portugal, Spain and Poland.

However, a report written by Deloitte (2016) highlighted that the following 9 MS (out of the EU-28) provided a low level of data quality with respect to CDW generation: Malta, Finland, Bulgaria, Latvia, Romania, Greece, Cyprus, Ireland, and Sweden. As such, the five highest and lowest MS generating CDW are highlighted in red and green respectively in Table 5.

From the results shown in Table 6, six MS with the highest and lowest CDW generation respectively were identified in Table 7, taking the overall performance in terms of the three parameters analysed into consideration.

Table 6. MS ranking with respect to the amount of CDW generated per parameter analysed
 (data from Table 5)

CDW vs turnover			CDW vs GDP			
MS	t/M€	MS	t/GDP in PPS	MS	CDW vs per capita t /capita	
1	Malta*	1080.69	Malta*	96.25	Malta*	2.41
2	Germany	377.17	Belgium	43.38	Belgium	1.43
3	Netherlands	299.96	Netherlands	39.19	Netherlands	1.39
4	Belgium	257.34	France	36.81	Austria	1.15
5	France	249.65	Germany	32.42	Germany	1.13
6	Italy	234.09	Austria	31.79	France	1.09
7	Austria	225.40	United Kingdom	28.47	Luxembourg	1.04
8	EU-28	213.47	Italy	24.65	United Kingdom	0.86
9	United Kingdom	206.55	EU-28	23.98	Denmark	0.75
10	Hungary	163.64	Denmark	21.18	EU-28	0.66
11	Denmark	148.48	Luxembourg	13.79	Italy	0.65
12	Latvia*	108.75	Estonia	13.01	Estonia	0.27
13	Czech Republic	96.64	Latvia*	12.96	Finland*	0.25
14	Estonia	91.72	Hungary	11.49	Czech Republic	0.24
15	Cyprus*	89.59	Czech Republic	9.81	Sweden*	0.24
16	Lithuania	87.43	Cyprus*	8.39	Latvia*	0.23
17	Luxembourg	83.34	Finland*	8.25	Hungary	0.22
18	Poland	71.37	Lithuania	7.10	Cyprus*	0.19
19	Croatia	69.66	Sweden*	6.86	Lithuania	0.15
20	Bulgaria*	66.81	Poland	5.96	Spain	0.12
21	Spain	57.35	Bulgaria*	5.74	Poland	0.11
22	Portugal	51.10	Croatia	5.11	Portugal	0.09
23	Finland*	47.33	Spain	4.92	Croatia	0.08
24	Greece*	43.31	Portugal	4.21	Bulgaria*	0.07
25	Slovakia	43.19	Slovakia	3.00	Slovakia	0.06
26	Sweden*	35.82	Slovenia	2.52	Slovenia	0.06
27	Romania*	29.11	Greece*	2.26	Ireland*	0.04
28	Slovenia	24.90	Romania*	1.47	Greece*	0.04
29	Ireland*	14.25	Ireland*	1.16	Romania*	0.02

* Countries with poor quality data (Deloitte, 2016)

Note: Highest values generating waste were marked in red, while the 5 lowest values were marked in green (not including MS with poor quality data)

Table 7. MS with the highest and lowest CDW generation rates

MS with the highest CDW generation rates	MS with the lowest CDW generation rates
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Austria •Germany •Netherlands •Belgium •France •Italy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Croatia •Slovenia •Slovakia •Poland •Portugal •Spain

4.2.2 Construction and demolition waste generation in EU-28 timeline

Eurostat waste statistics (2017) regarding waste generation in CD activities gives information on the kg of CDW and CDWE per capita for each MS since 2004 with an interval of two years from 2004 to 2014. The total amount of CDWE has been available since 2004, while CDW data has only been available from 2010 to 2014 as the amount of soil and dredging spoil generated is only specified for those years. Therefore, in order to analyse a broader period of time, data from 2004 to 2014 was used in this section despite the inclusion of excavated soils and dredging spoil.

In addition, the amount of CDWE per capita for MS with higher and lower waste generation rates is shown in Figure 7. In general, the amount of CDWE generated in the MS has been kept constant over the last few years. In particular, the total CDWE generation in the Netherlands has steadily increased to around 76.51% since 2004, while Spain has decreased its generation to around 40.68%. Other MS such as Germany, Italy, Slovakia or Portugal have generated similar amounts of CDWE since 2004.

Figure 7. CDWE generation per capita from 2004 to 2014 for MS with higher and lower waste generation rates, denoted in red and green respectively

In addition, the effect of transposing the WFD into MS national regulations of high and low MS generating waste was also explored. For this, the kg of CDWE per capita was collected from 2004 to 2014 as well as the year in which the WFD was transposed or a specific CDW regulation was implemented (Table 8).

Table 8. CDWE generation (kg per capita) and the year of WFD transposition or CDW regulation for high and low MS generating CDW as well as for the EU-28 MS

	MS	Year of WFD transposition or CDW regulation implementation	CDWE generation (kg per capita)					
			2004	2006	2008	2010	2012	2014
Highest CDW generation rates	Austria	2010	3418	3788	3772	2502	3970	4714
	Belgium	2012	1059	1241	1442	1667	1518	1521
	France	2009	3359	3552	3942	4022	3770	3447
	Germany	2012	2322	2386	2402	2336	2456	2550
	Italy	2010	852	900	1185	1001	890	850
	Netherlands	2011	3048	3470	3581	4698	4725	5380
Lowest CDW generation rates	Croatia	2011	150	4	30	2	158	146
	Poland	2012	44	371	182	547	404	447
	Portugal	2008	250	343	129	168	88	145
	Slovakia	2012	261	171	242	331	149	256
	Slovenia	2008	455	496	681	737	260	395
	Spain	2008	1079	1066	978	815	559	439
	EU-28	2008	1552	1681	1725	1707	1661	1692

Note: The year of WFD or CDW national regulation implementation is highlighted in grey

Figure 8 shows the trend of CDWE generation (kg per capita) before and after transposing the WFD into national policy frameworks or implementing specific national CDW regulations.

Note: High and low MS generating CDW are denoted in red and green respectively

Figure 8. CDW generation before and after WFD transposition or specific CDW regulation for the EU-28 and high and low MS generating waste (Villoria Sáez and Osmani, 2018)⁵

The average waste generation for EU-28 has remained constant after six years of implementing the WFD. This may be explained due to the delay of some countries in transposing the WFD into their national regulations. While waste generation per capita in all MS decreased after the transposition of the WFD, this increased in the Netherlands, Germany and Austria. This could be explained by an increase in CD activities for those countries. As such, other parameters such as construction and the economic activities of each MS also need to be considered when assessing CDW generation.

4.2.3 Construction and demolition waste streams

Eurostat does provide information about waste streams generated in each MS. In this regard, two different waste classifications are currently used by MS for CDW data compilation (Eurostat, 2010):

- European Waste Catalogue classification (EWC-STAT): is the Eurostat waste classification system and uses three digit level codes (European Parliament, 2002). This classification is substance-oriented and contains 13 categories, which are subdivided into individual waste types (European Commission, 2010). Statistics of EWC codes do not include information regarding the waste generating activity, except

⁵ CDW landfill and generation data was taken from Eurostat (2017) and landfill taxes were taken from the sources mentioned in Table 3.

for some EWC codes such as “W121”, which specifically refers to mineral waste from CD.

- European List of Waste classification (ELW): contains 17 codes for the different types of CDW. In addition, the WFD sets the quantitative target for CDW recovery 2020 based on this classification. In addition, this classification also allows the activities generating this waste to be tracked (European Parliament, 2000).

Despite the two waste classifications above being well-known and established, the Regulation (EC) 2150/2002 on waste statistics requires MS to report statistical data on waste generation using EWC-Stat codes. As such, the data shown in the figures of this section refer to EWC-STAT codes.

If excavated soils and dredging spoils are not considered, the different EWC-STAT categories generated in each EU-28 MS in 2014 were mineral wastes from CD activities ⁶(Figure 9). An example of CDW generation in Italy using ELW codes was presented by Rigamonti and Pantini (2016) at WG1 MINEA Workshop (MINEA Cost Action, 2016). This work concluded that the most abundant CDW stream is mixed CDW (ELW code 170904), which may be indicative of a scarce source separation at worksites. However, mixed CDW appears to be mainly composed of concrete, soils, tiles and ceramics with a rather low level of impurities such as wood, glass and plastics.

⁶ Mineral waste from CD originates during CD activities and encompasses: concrete, bricks and gypsum waste, insulation materials, mixed construction wastes containing glass, plastics and wood, and hydrocarbonised road-surfacing material waste. The latter are hazardous when containing organic pollutants.

Other mineral wastes include asbestos materials, mineral wastes from mining and quarrying blasting material and grinding bodies casting cores and moulds and, finally, linings and refractories from all thermal processes. EUROSTAT 2010. Guidance on classification of waste according to EWC-Stat categories. Supplement to the Manual for the Implementation of the Regulation (EC) No 2150/2002 on Waste Statistics. European Commission.

Figure 9. Percentage of each waste stream generated in each MS in 2014 (Eurostat, 2017)

The EU-28 average highlighted that the dominant generating waste streams in 2014 were mineral wastes from CD activities, followed by metal and wood (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Waste streams generation in the construction sector in 2014 (EU-28) (Eurostat, 2017)

In addition, it is critical to evaluate the amount and streams of CDW generated in the different CD activities. However, Eurostat (2017) waste statistics do not offer separate data for excavation, construction, refurbishment and demolition waste generation or for associated types of project such as public works, buildings and civil structures. Therefore, it was not possible to obtain detailed aggregated data on CDW generation with respect to the types of CD activities. This aspect has been explored by some EU funded projects, but results are only available for a particular MS and for a specific type of building CD activity. For example, the DEMOCLES project, conducted in France and whose results were presented by Mtibaa (2016) at the WG1 MINEA Workshop, analysed the amount of CDW generated during the finishing work on six renovation/demolition projects and concluded that they represent approximately 25% of all CDW generated, out of which 48% are inert waste (bricks, ceramics and sanitary furniture), 47% non-hazardous wastes (gypsum based products, windows, etc.) and 5% hazardous wastes (mainly gas discharge lamps, treated wood and asbestos).

4.3 Construction and demolition waste recovery rates

The severity of CDW generation not only depends on the amount generated, but also on its management. Eurostat (2017) provides statistics on waste management per waste category, without specifying the activity or industry. Therefore, CDW management data is only based on the waste category “mineral waste from CD” instead of reporting the total waste generated in the construction sector. Eurostat (2017) provided statistics for the following waste management options for each MS from 2010-2014:

- landfill / disposal;
- incineration (disposal and energy recovery);
- recovery other than energy recovery – backfilling; and

- recovery other than energy recovery - except backfilling.

Figure 11 shows the management of mineral CDW carried out in EU-28 from 2010 to 2014. Mineral CDW generated are mainly recovered and smaller amounts are actually incinerated. In the EU-28 the percentage of CDW that has been landfilled has decreased since 2010 mainly due to the initiatives and instruments (legislative, financial, technology, etc.) that have been launched to promote CDW recovery and recycling. In this sense, for the year 2014, EU-28 has already reached the target set for the year 2020.

Figure 11. Management of mineral CDW carried out in the EU-28 since 2010 (Eurostat, 2017)

Figure 12 summarises waste management options used for mineral CDW across MS in 2014 (Eurostat, 2017). The percentage of waste landfilled in 2014 varies from less than 1% (Netherlands) to over 99% (Greece). The amount of CDW that is incinerated is minimal except in Finland, Denmark and Belgium, where there is a significant use of wood for construction activities. Similarly, the amount of backfilling appears to be small except for Ireland, Malta and the Czech Republic. Belgium’s low recovery rate could be due to the misallocation of excavated soils in the waste category mineral CDW.

Figure 12. Management of mineral CDW across the MS for 2014 (Eurostat, 2017)

Significant differences in CDW management among the EU MS can be due to the following parameters that differ from country to country: construction and demolition waste management regulations, landfill taxes and bans, construction and demolition waste management facilities, the costs of primary raw materials (PRM) and the existence of a market for secondary raw materials for the EU construction industry. These are examined in more detail in the sections below.

- Construction and demolition waste management regulations:** different regulations with regard to CDW also reveal important differences between EU MS (Table 2). Some MS with high CDW recovery rates, such as Poland, do not have specific regulations regarding CDW, while others – such as Austria, Estonia or the Netherlands – rely mostly on soft steering frameworks such as Waste Management Plans or regulations pertaining to local authorities (Deloitte, 2016, Deloitte, 2015a).
- Landfill taxes and bans:** low recovery rates may be explained by low landfill taxes and bans or small penalties for waste disposal (Bartelings et al., 2005). Figure 13 and Figure 14 show the relation between the landfill taxes and the percentage of CDW landfilled and recovered for high and low MS generating CDW. Germany and Croatia were not included in the study as they don't have landfill taxation. However, in order to broaden the study, Denmark and the United Kingdom were included because they surpass 90% of the CDW recovery, have good quality CDW data and a landfill tax (Deloitte, 2016).

Figure 13. Relation between landfill tax and % of CDW landfilled in 2014 (Villoria Sáez and Osmani, 2018)⁷

Figure 14. Relation between landfill tax and % of CDW recovered in 2014 (Villoria Sáez and Osmani, 2018)⁸

Results in Figure 14 show that no correlation was found between the landfill tax and the percentage of CDW landfilled or recovery, despite the fact that landfill taxes are often considered as a driver for CDW recovery and recycling. For instance, Denmark and the United Kingdom have high disposal costs and low rates of landfilling, while Austria, the Netherlands, Italy and Portugal also have low landfilling rates in spite of

⁷ CDW landfill and generation data was taken from Eurostat (2017) and landfill taxes were taken from the sources mentioned in Table 3. Landfill taxes used for United Kingdom and Denmark were 84.4£ (96.24€) and DKK 475 (64€) respectively.

⁸ CDW landfill and generation data was taken from Eurostat (2017) and landfill taxes were taken from the sources mentioned in Table 3. Landfill taxes used for the United Kingdom and Denmark were 84.4£ (96.24€) and DKK 475 (64€) respectively.

having low disposal costs. It is interesting to note that countries such as Denmark and the United Kingdom have landfill taxes and good recovery rates, while Germany has a high level of CDW recovery without using landfill taxation. This can be explained by other factors possibly affecting the waste management carried out in each MS.

- Construction and demolition waste management facilities: presently there is no database available that contains all waste treatment facilities specifically for CDW in the EU. However, a first approach in this report has been developed analysing the amount of waste generated and the overall waste facilities in each MS.

Figure 15 shows the amount of waste recovered and the number of waste facilities in each MS in 2014. In general, countries with higher recovery rates, such as the United Kingdom and Germany, have a dense network of CDW management facilities, while other countries such as Croatia and Slovakia have a smaller number or inadequate distribution of CDW management facilities (Deloitte, 2016).

Figure 15. Amount of CDW recovered and number of waste facilities for each MS in 2014 (Eurostat, 2017)

- Cost of primary raw materials (PRM) and existence of a market for secondary raw materials (SRM) for the EU construction industry: some countries, such as Spain, have sufficient and available PRM, providing enough quality at a moderate cost (Deloitte, 2016). Therefore, SRM markets are difficult to develop under current market conditions in Spain and other countries with a similar situation, especially if they do not implement other initiatives to promote CDW recovery. For example, a tool to improve CDW logistics was developed by Clean-Way in Hungary and was presented at WG1 MINEA Workshop and included in the WBoA (MINEA Cost Action, 2016). This tool collects and shows real-time data of all the construction sites where CDW is being generated, indicating the site location, details of waste producer, the amount of waste generated and data of SRM wanted (Petrovszki, 2016).

Low recovery rates can also be explained by a lack of confidence in recycled construction materials despite the fact that they fulfil technical requirements and quality standards equivalent to the PRM (European Commission, 2016). The low amounts of CDW recovered in Greece, which is shown in Figure 12, could be related to the non-existence of an effective regulation framework for the use of recycled materials as well as the lack of legal requirements with respect to recycled materials or recycled content in construction materials.

By contrast, dedicated initiatives are being implemented in the Netherlands, Luxembourg, Belgium and Italy to reduce CDW landfill and promote the use of secondary raw materials (SRM) used in construction projects, namely in building and road applications. For instance, the Italian legislation D.M.11/01/2017 sets the following minimum percentages of waste to be used in the construction, renovation or maintenance of publicly-funded buildings:

- concrete must have a recycled content of at least 5%;
- bricks used for masonry and ceilings must have a recycled content of at least 10%, while ceramic elements for roofs, floors and façades must have at least 5%;
- plastic materials, have a recycled content of at least 30% by weight of the overall plastic; and
- plasterboard must have a recycled content of at least 5%.

In addition, a study conducted in Germany and presented during the WG1 MINEA Workshop (MINEA Cost Action, 2016) developed a material flow analysis of stocks and flows to assess CDW recovery potential (Deilmann et al., 2016). This work concluded that PRM savings by use of SRM in building construction might increase from 7% to 21% –under optimistic framework conditions– by 2050 in Germany.

4.4 Performance against EU 2020 construction and demolition waste recovery target

The WFD includes a specific target for the reuse, recycling and other material recovery of CDW: *'by 2020, the preparing for re-use, recycling and other material recovery, including backfilling operations using waste to substitute other materials, of non-hazardous CDW excluding naturally occurring material defined in category 170504 in the list of waste shall be increased to a minimum of 70 % by weight.'*

MS shall provide data on the state of preparation for reuse, recycling and material recovery of CDW. CDW recovery rates were directly reported by all EU MS except for Greece, Germany and Luxembourg. Figure 16 shows the recovery rates of mineral waste from CD activities from 2010 to 2014.

* Data was not available for Greece from 2010-2014, neither for Germany and Luxembourg for 2014.

Figure 16. Recovery rates of mineral CDW in EU since 2010 to 2014 (Eurostat, 2017)

Results reveal that the construction and demolition mineral waste recovery rate in 2014 increased significantly in Finland, Malta, Croatia and Bulgaria if compared with that of 2010, while it decreased in Sweden, Cyprus and Belgium. In addition and as shown in Figure 16, some MS have already reached the 70 % recovery target set in the Waste Framework Directive for the year 2020, whilst other MS still need to take further measures to improve their rate.

Moreover, the definition of the CDW recovery target in the WFD enables MS to include the volumes used for backfilling in the calculation of their national CDW recovery target. But the WFD also requires that MS “*shall take measures to promote high quality recycling*”, which seems rather contradictory. Furthermore, as the WFD itself does not provide a definition for backfilling, there is relative confusion among MS concerning the term backfilling and its application as a recovery or a disposal operation (Deloitte, 2016). As such, the inclusion or exclusion of the amounts reported as backfilling influences the calculation of the recovery rate and results in great differences between some MS. This reiterates the confusion and incoherence surrounding the definitions and reporting of recovery rates among MS. This fact was also addressed and discussed during the breakout session and final debate of the WG1 MINEA Workshop, and was highlighted as one of the main CDW recovery challenges to be addressed by the EU (MINEA Cost Action, 2016).

The recovery rates provided by Eurostat do not give information regarding backfilling directly. However, statistics covering the management carried out for mineral CDW were used to assess the percentage of backfilling for each country (Figure 17). Although Germany and Luxemburg did not report their recovery rates directly to Eurostat for 2014 (Figure 16), both countries reported the management carried out for CDW in 2014. This issue evidences the deficient quality of available data and the inconsistency and differences of data collection methods used by MS. Finally, the recovery rates for MS were obtained using the data provided regarding the type of waste management.

Figure 17. Recovery rates of mineral waste from CD in EU in 2014

Countries exhibiting higher differences of recovery rate depending on whether backfilling is included or excluded are: Iceland, Ireland, Malta and the Czech Republic. Therefore, backfilling will be a determinant factor for some MS in order to meet the EU target for 2020. No common practice among MS to manage CDW recovery, mainly due to the different composition of CDW and national legislation, is a key indicator of differences between MS in terms of CDW recovery performance.

4.5 Landfilling versus recovery forecast

In 2015, a report written by Hogg et al. (2015) for EUNOMIA and the European Commission developed a CDW model to quantify the impact of different scenarios with regard to the following issues: economic, environment, job creation and greenhouse gas emissions. The report presented the overall costs and benefits of two scenarios for every MS up to the year 2035. The scenarios analysed were:

- A business as usual scenario (BAU) in which no attempts will be made to increase recovery rates. The amount of CDW will keep on growing at a rate defined by the GDP times a growth multiplier⁹.
- A more ambitious scenario (MA) to meet the recycling target of 70% by 2020. However, quantities of backfilling were excluded and therefore increased CDW recycling is needed.

The Hogg et al. (2015) study was based on Eurostat waste code W121: “*mineral waste from construction and demolition*” data for 2010 and 2012. The overall increase in waste generated

⁹ The growth multiplier was set to 0.5 in wealthier MS and to 1 in less wealthy MS. In 2020, it was set to 0.5 for all MS. HOGG, D., VERGUNST, T., ELLIOTT, T., ELLIOTT, L., CORBIN, M. & BALLINGER, A. 2015. Further development of the European reference Model on Waste Generation and Management. Final Report. Luxembourg: European Commission.

and treated in the EU is the same in both scenarios. In particular, the overall amount of CDW generated (excluding excavated soil) is 356 Mtonnes in 2012 and 385 Mtonnes in 2020. The increase in the amounts of waste treated follows the same pattern, increasing from 296 Mtonnes in 2012 to 320 Mtonnes in 2020.

Table 9 shows the forecast of the amount of waste landfilled and recycled for MS, with the highest and lowest CDW generation taking the two scenarios into account. From the twelve MS examined by Hogg et al. (2015), seven MS had already reached the target for the MA scenario and were thus not further analysed.

Table 9. CDW landfill versus recovery forecast of two different scenarios for high and low MS generating CDW, based on data from Hogg et al. (2015).

MS	Treatment	Business as usual scenario (Thousand Tonnes)					More ambitious scenario (Thousand tonnes)				
		2015	2020	2025	2030	2035	2015	2020	2025	2030	2035
Austria	CDW recycling rate was 92% in 2012.*										
Belgium	CDW recycling rate was 98% in 2012.*										
France	Recycling	36,962	38,847	40,829	42,911	45,100	39,630	46,326	48,690	51,173	53,784
	Landfill	21,228	22,311	23,449	24,646	25,903	19,453	17,334	18,219	19,148	20,125
Germany	CDW recycling rate was 85% in 2012.*										
Italy	CDW recycling rate was 96% in 2012.*										
Netherlands	CDW recycling rate was 100% in 2012.*										
Croatia	Recycling	134	144	151	159	167	152	195	205	216	227
	Landfill	127	135	142	149	157	108	84	88	92	97
Poland	Recycling	2,162	2,312	2,429	2,553	2,684	2,188	2,388	2,509	2,637	2,772
	Landfill	247	264	277	291	306	247	264	277	291	306
Portugal	CDW recycling rate was 91% in 2012.*										
Slovakia	Recycling	172	184	193	203	213	224	333	350	368	386
	Landfill	273	292	306	322	338	220	143	150	157	165
Slovenia	CDW recycling rate was 91% in 2012.*										
Spain	Recycling	19,098	20,422	21,464	22,559	23,710	19,276	20,931	21,998	23,121	24,300
	Landfill	4,445	4,754	4,996	5,251	5,519	4,445	4,754	4,996	5,251	5,519

* The rate was already above the 70% recycling target specified by the 'More Ambitious' scenario and therefore no results were shown in the study.

4.6 Construction and demolition waste recovery challenges

From the current situation of CDW generation and management in the EU shown in the previous sections, the main CDW recovery challenges in EU-28, which still need to be addressed (Arm et al., 2017, Oyenuga et al., 2015), have been summarized in 4 main topics, as shown in **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.**: (1) Legislative, (2) Data quality and harmonization, (3) Improved reverse logistics, and (4) Market readiness for secondary materials.

Table 9. Current CDW recovery challenges in EU-28 Member States

LEGISLATIVE

- Few MS have developed specific national regulations for CDW management and most of the countries rely on Waste Management Plans or local regulations.
- There is ineffective enforcement of CDW regulations.
- Inefficient incentives (penalties and bans) that help prevent landfilling from being the cheapest option for waste management

DATA QUALITY AND HARMONIZATION

- There is a lack of harmonisation in terms of definitions regarding CDW management issues. For instance, backfilling will be a determinant factor for some MS in terms of their ability to meet the EU recovery target for 2020.
- There is a lack of standardized and transparent data collection methods among MS with respect to harmonisation of CDW definitions and waste stream classifications (EWL and ELW)
- There is a poor quality of data available regarding waste generation and recovery rates. For instance, the information regarding CDW is not updated in real time as the latest published and accessible data is for 2014.
- Two different waste stream classifications are currently being used by MS for CDW data compilation and analysis (EWC and ELW). CDW data (provided by Eurostat) uses the EWC classification, while the recycling target for 2020 set by the WFD refers to the ELW classification.
- Poor standardization of technical data of recycled materials.

IMPROVED REVERSE LOGISTICS

- Detailed information in terms of types and capacities of CDW management facilities in order to determine future requirements
- Greater number and better distribution of CDW management facilities
- Poor cross-border coordination between regions

MARKET READINESS FOR SECONDARY MATERIALS

- Guarantee the purity of the waste to be recycled
- Enhance on-site separation.
- Improve workers' knowledge and training.
- Determine minimum quality specifications for waste inputs and harmonise them across MS (when possible)
- Guarantee the supply of long-term feedstock.
- Optimise CDW sorting and recovering technologies
- Provide greater incentives and economic incitements for using recycled products
- Assure the quality of recycled products

5 CONSTRUCTION AND DEMOLITION WASTE RECYCLING AND RECOVERY APPROACHES

This section aims to provide an overview of the most common and emerging technologies for CDW recycling and recovery in the EU. Figure 18 shows the different CDW recovery approaches and associated technologies, which are described below.

Figure 18. Current CDW recovery approaches and associated technologies (Villoria Sáez and Osmani, 2018)

5.1 Construction and demolition waste source collection and separation

The quality of CDW is directly influenced by the performance carried out in the construction and/or demolition site. For instance, one of the main difficulties for waste recovery is the collection of mixed waste (instead of site-sorting) and the inefficient mechanical sorting of the mixed waste. Therefore, the operatives' attitude and training regarding CDW management is essential for implementing CDW sorting techniques. Additionally, more efficient waste sorting technologies are needed to generate cleaner recovery CDW (Kulatunga et al., 2006). Recovery requires CDW streams to be thoroughly separated either onsite or within waste sorting facilities (Meinander et al., 2012):

- **Onsite sorting:** waste is sorted onsite before transportation. In this case, waste streams should be segregated at source, reducing the risk of contamination and improving the quality and recycling rate of all fractions. Onsite sorting, however, increases the number of waste fractions, and consequently the number of waste containers, thus increasing

collection costs and requiring greater space on site. The most common waste collection methods depend on the amount of waste generated and include: bags, wheelie bins, waste skips, and roll-on and roll-off containers (Figure 19).

Figure 19. CDW collection methods

- Sorting CDW in the recycling facility: reduces the number of waste fractions and required containers, and thus the cost and efforts associated with onsite sorting are also reduced. The mixed waste is commonly separated in a series of mechanical processes, which separate different materials based on their mechanical properties.

CDW separation is based on different identification methods and combinations of these, mainly focused on the size, density, magnetic or optical properties of the waste to be segregated. The most commonly used technologies for sorting waste are: size separation, gravity/density separation, metal separation, and automatic sensors that include microwave sensors, optic sensors and X-rays (Capel, 2008b, Lund Neidel and Bjørn Jakobsen, 2013, Vrancken et al., 2017). These technologies can be used in portable waste facilities as well as in stationary recovery plants.

5.1.1 Particle size separation

Size separation equipment splits the incoming CDW according to particle sizes. The key particle size separation technologies include ‘trommel separators’ and ‘vibrating screens’.

- Trommel separators (also known as drum screens) are the most commonly used technologies for size separation (Içelli et al., 2003, Chen et al., 2010). CDW is fed into a rotating perforated cylinder drum, which allows smaller materials to drop out during the rotation process, while larger-sized materials pass through the trommel. Figure 21 shows an example of a trommel used onsite.

Figure 20. CDW collection methods (Revolv, 2017)

Figure 21. Trommel for onsite waste segregation (Ultra Spreader International, 2017)

- Vibrating screens consist of a drive that induces vibration, a screen cloth that causes particle separation and a deck which holds the screen cloth and the drive, acting as the mode of transport for the vibration. High frequency vibrating screens usually operate at an inclined angle, varying between 0 and 45 degrees.

Figure 22. Vibrating screen (Lund Neidel and Bjørn Jakobsen, 2013)

5.1.2 Material density separation

CDW separation can be performed through density sorting using wet or dry methods.

- The wet method is mainly used to separate mixed CDW characterized by fewer differences in the specific mass among them. This method is used to separate mixed CDW containing glass, metals, plastics and mixed plastics. There are three types of wet method: thin flow, jog sorting and heavy liquid sorting (Japan External Trade Organization, 2013).
 - *Thin flow* sorting uses the moving speed of solid particles fed into a thin flow on a horizontal or tilted panel, which differs depending on the fractions' densities.
 - *Jig sorting* separates materials by letting water flow in up-and-down pulses through a layer of solid particles on fixed mesh to form stratification based on the specific mass of materials.

- *Heavy liquid sorting* separates particles into fractions with a smaller density and particles with a larger density by suspending them in a liquid with a specific density (heavy liquid).

Figure 23. Example of Jig sorting (Gundupalli et al., 2017)

- The dry method uses air streams to separate CDW (Mulder et al., 2007). One of the most popular dry methods is the air classifier, which separates light and heavy particles by vibrating a tilted deck sideways and generating upward air flow from the bottom of the deck at the same time ((Japan External Trade Organization, 2013, Lund Neidel and Bjørn Jakobsen, 2013). Particles on the deck move the slope upward due to the vibration and the friction with the deck. However, the upward air flow decreases the friction coefficient, making particles with low specific gravity move downward and particles with high specific gravity move upward, thus separating the particles (Japan External Trade Organization, 2013).

Figure 24. Example of a common air classifier (Lund Neidel and Bjørn Jakobsen, 2013)

5.1.3 Metal separation

The widely used sorting methods for waste metals are: magnetic and electromagnetic separators.

- Magnetic separators are specifically employed for the separation of iron metals and non-ferrous metals. In this technique, waste is subjected to a conveyor belt with a series of sensors underneath. These sensors analyse the material over the whole width of the conveyor belt by means of magnets. As soon as metallic particles are detected, electronic signals are sent to the central computerized control unit. The compressed air jets, individually controlled, push the detected metals over the diverter gate (Steinert, 2017).
- Electromagnetic separators use a rotary drum type separator which is in-line with Neodymium magnets with alternating north and south poles, as shown in Figure 25. This method separates ferrous and non-ferrous metals (aluminium, copper, magnesium and silver) from the rest of the materials (Goudsmit Magnetic Systems, 2017). However, it is not effective for separating zinc, brass and tin, as well as high alloyed steels (Lund Neidel and Bjørn Jakobsen, 2013).

Figure 25. Functional principle of Eddie current separator (Gundupalli et al., 2017)

5.1.4 Microwave sensors

Microwave sensors measure the interaction of electromagnetic fields at microwave frequencies, which include a region that lies between infrared and radio frequencies (Figure 26). When a microwave absorbing material is located in electric field energy, it experiences a rapid volumetric heating. Unlike conventional heating methods, this heating effect is almost instantaneous (Kostas et al., 2017). Although this method could be applied for the drying of wet materials, not all materials have the ability to absorb microwaves.

5.1.5 Optic sensor separation

Optical or hyperspectral imaging (HIS) technology unfolds in different technologies, depending on the spectral distinctiveness of the items to be sorted, such as Visible (VIS), Near Infrared (NIR) and Short-wave Infrared (SWI) (Figure 26).

Figure 26. Electromagnetic Spectrum Illustrating SWIR Wavelength Range (Edmund optics, 2017)

Key technologies for CDW classification using optic sensor separators include: Near infrared spectrum sensors (NIR) and Visual spectrometry (VIS):

- Near infrared (NIR) spectrum sensors can distinguish between different materials based on the way they reflect light. CDW is fed onto a conveyor belt and it is further detected by the NIR sensor. If the sensor detects material to be separated, it commands the control unit to blow the appropriate valves of the ejection module at the end of the conveyor belt (Vegas et al., 2015). The detected materials are separated from the material flow by jets of compressed air and thus the material is finally divided into different fractions in the separation chamber (Figure 27).

Figure 27. Functional principle of NIR sensor-based sorting technology (Vegas et al., 2015)

- Visual spectrometry (VIS) is based on camera units which distinguish between all colours that are visible via photo recognition. Then, air jets are used to sort out the materials into different slots.

Figure 28. Functional principle of VIS sorting technology (Japan External Trade Organization, 2013)

Some methodologies were developed to use more than one region of the light spectrum and thus both technologies can be combined to achieve better segregation of the waste than using one single region (Vrancken et al., 2017).

5.1.6 X-ray sensors

X-ray sensors use X-ray photons to impact a material and detect X-rays emissions depending on the molecular density of the material. Therefore, it can be used to distinguish between different types of materials and to separate contaminant plastics or metals (Capel, 2008b, De Jong et al., 2003, Firsching et al., 2013). The production of X-ray energy is carried out by applying a very high voltage in a vacuum tube, and the detection is typically done by a charge collection device behind the material, which is connected to an electronic system to estimate the transmitted energy (Vrancken et al., 2017). X-ray sorting can be categorized into two types: Dual Energy X-ray Transmission (DE-XRT) and X-ray Fluorescence (XRF) (Gundupalli et al., 2017).

5.2 Construction and demolition waste processing

Current CDW processing systems can be divided into two groups: systems aimed at reducing the particle size of the material (shredders, chippers, grinders, granulators and hammer mills) and processes aimed at reducing the volume of CDW (compactors and balers). Further, multifunctional equipment can also be found combining some of the previous methods (WRAP and WSP Environmental Limited, 2009).

5.2.1 Material particle size reduction systems

Systems aimed at reducing the particle size of the materials are: shredders, grinders, chippers, granulators and hammer mills.

- Shredders vary depending on their function and can be categorized by the type of process they employ. The internal mechanical processes may include cutting, grinding,

hammering and compression and in some cases they may include shaking/sorting mechanisms (Wastecare Corporation, 2017). Internal machinery may travel in rotary, lateral or vertical directions and can be equipped with different kinds of cutting systems such as: a vertical/horizontal shaft design and single-shaft shredder (the most traditional blade system), or multiple-shaft shredders (two, three and four-shaft) which employ various methods of forcing materials between and against blades (Capel, 2008a). Shredding solutions of choice typically involve low speed and high force units that slowly tear material apart, minimizing problems such as embedding metal in plastic during the shredding process (LeBlanc, 2016).

- Grinders use abrasion, often combined with compression to pulverize materials, usually to produce granular products. Wheels, drums and plates may be used in the processes. Grinders may be either high or low speed machines depending on the type of use (Wastecare Corporation, 2017).
- Chippers use high speed rotary knives to turn the material into flakes or chips. They can be manually or automatically fed, and may be single or multiple stage machines. They may also employ single or multiple drums or wheels with single or multiple knives (Wastecare Corporation, 2017).
- Granulators are frequently used for plastic recycling. These units use knives -rather than abrasive surfaces - to reduce the material to fine particles. Some granulators are equipped with thermoforming units that transform the output into easily handled scrap or production parts.
- Hammer mills are used to pulverize materials. The most common configuration is a chamber containing a rotary drum with swivelling hammers of hardened bar or chain (Hadžikadić and Avdaković, 2017).

All of the above technologies may also be used to reduce the size of onsite CDW. This will help to increase the volume of CDW streams in each skip and thus reduce CDW collection and transport costs as fewer containers will be needed (WRAP and WSP Environmental Limited, 2009).

Figure 29. Example of an onsite shredder (Timberwolf Ltd., 2017)

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5.2.2 Material volume reduction systems

Material volume reduction systems include compactors and balers.

- Compactors, which comprise manual or mechanical compaction techniques, are used to increase the quantity of waste material that can be stored in smaller waste containers, reducing CDW collection and transport costs. They can reduce the volume of CDW by a ratio of up to 6:1, depending on the materials being compacted (WRAP and WSP Environmental Limited, 2009). In general, compactors have been widely used for the following waste flows: plastics, paper, cardboard and light metals. However, traditional compactors should be avoided for rigid materials that cannot be compressed such as wood, metal, glass and demolition wastes. For rigid materials such as wood, it is recommended that a roller type compactor be used.
- Balers compact CDW into a high density and bundle it with wire so that it retains its shape, though some balers rely on the post compaction adhesion of CDW to retain the bale's shape. This shape is usually a rectangular block whose dimensions typically vary from 3 feet to 8 feet (WRAP and WSP Environmental Limited, 2009).

5.3 Construction and demolition waste recovery and treatment

By and large, mechanical, biological and chemical procedures can be used to recover and treat CDW.

- Mechanical treatment is represented by a physical method in which the waste is cut and shredded into granulates, flakes, pellets or powder of appropriate quality for further manufacturing
- Biological treatment can reduce the weight of wastes through a fermentation process involving microorganisms and produce organic fertilizers. However, CDW do not usually have biodegradable fractions, so this method is not commonly used (Vrancken et al., 2017).
- Chemical treatment involves chemical treatment. One such example involves decomposing waste plastics to return them to monomer.

For some CDW streams, recovery involves complex technical processes and requires specialised machinery, but others can be recovered more simply (Wheeler and Rome, 2002). Mechanical methods are the most commonly used for the recovery of inert materials as no alteration of the materials is involved during the process. However, other CDW streams require different recovery procedures. For instance, paper waste can be broken into fibres to form new paper; waste metals, plastic and glass can be melted or grounded down; and organic waste can be composted.

6 SELECTION RATIONALE FOR CASE STUDIES

The two most significant waste flows generated within the EU CD sector in 2014 were selected (Figure 9 and Figure 10). These are: mineral wastes from CD activities and metals. Mineral waste includes:

- concrete, bricks, and gypsum waste,
- insulation materials,
- mixed construction wastes containing glass, plastics and wood, and
- asphalt.

Mineral waste from CD cover a variety of different mixed waste streams, and special attention has been paid to CDW separation techniques (Mousavi et al., 2016). Therefore, a literature review was conducted, covering sorting technologies for mixed CDW.

By and large, current recycling and recovery technologies are associated with large and heavy mineral waste streams of importance to fulfil the EU recycling target, which is weight-based. Therefore, no glass, plastic or insulation materials were considered for this report as they are lightweight wastes and are commonly generated and treated in other industries. In addition, several related studies have been published regarding technologies for sorting and recovering these wastes, mainly for paper (Rahman et al., 2014) and plastics (Dodhiba and Fujita, 2004, Al-Salem et al., 2009, Sadat-Shojai and Bakhshandeh, 2011, Wu et al., 2013, Wang et al., 2015).

Asbestos waste was also included in this study due to its countless harmful effects in humans when exposed in building rehabilitation or demolition works. For instance, asbestos waste management became a priority in the EU countries. It is one of the most feared contaminants because inhaling asbestos fibres can cause asbestosis, lung cancer and mesothelioma (World Health Organization, 2000). All asbestos containing materials are classified as carcinogenic substances and their use is consequently restricted in great parts of the world.

Based on the above, the following CDW streams (case studies) and associated recovery technologies are examined in this report:

1. Concrete, bricks and ceramics (CBC)
2. Gypsum (G)
3. Wood (W)
4. Asphalt (AP)
5. Metals (M)
6. Asbestos (AB)

7 CONSTRUCTION AND DEMOLITION WASTE SORTING TECHNOLOGIES

This section assesses CDW sorting technologies, which are typically common to the selected six case studies.

Recent research has produced some important results that can lead to a significant advancement in CDW. In particular, special attention has been paid to sorting technologies useful to separate CDW streams that led to cleaner and separated waste. These, in turn, facilitate their reprocessing and upcycling (Mousavi et al., 2016).

The European-funded CANDY (Compact, highly mobile, next generation, construction, demolition and excavation waste recovery system) project aimed at improving the technologies for CDW recycling by enhancing the quality of recycled aggregates (CANDY project, 2014). For this, a wet sorting technology was developed and set in a recycling plant in Stuttgart, Germany. This technology included the following phases:

- feed arrangement,
- aggregate screening,
- attrition using Rotomax Logwasher,
- sand washing,
- aggregate sizing and
- water treatment & recycling.

Similarly, a wet technology was presented at MINEA WBoA (MINEA Cost Action, 2016) for sorting organic content from CDW. The tool is based on density separation using water, and up to 40% of the organic carbon was successfully separated from the rest of CDW. In general, the use of wet technologies for CDW separation provide environmental benefits such as greater mobility and a reduced plant footprint arising from recycling plant operations.

Furthermore, air jigging sorting, which is well-established for municipal solid waste, was used to separate CDW from other unwanted impurities and waste flows that can decrease the quality of recycled aggregate such as gypsum, wood and paper (Ambros et al., 2017). It was demonstrated that it is possible to simultaneously carry out both high-sorting process concentration of selected waste flows and the removal of low-density contaminants (paper, gypsum, wood, etc.).

Advanced automated sorting techniques, which have been successfully researched and developed for high quality sorting of plastics from municipal waste and for glass recycling, have also been investigated in the field of CDW recycling (Hollstein et al., 2016). For instance, de Jong et al. (2005) and Mulder et al. (2007) analysed the automatic colour sorting process using the Scan & Sort CombiSense 1200 equipment in Germany. This technology uses a high-speed camera and a conductivity sensor which analyses the size, shape, colour and position of CDW

on the belt. The information is then modelled further through a computer which generates impulses instructing the nozzles to blow out single particles or allow them to pass. This colour technique can sort up to 40 tonnes of CDW per hour and can be effectively used for wood, glass and gypsum removal from mixed CDW.

Moreover, the Dual Energy (DE) X-ray transmission technique was investigated by Mulder et al. (2007), who found that this type of automatic sorting is especially useful for the separation of organic and inorganic materials. Especially noteworthy is that the sorting of wood at high purity and recovery is possible. CDW was sorted using this method and was screened in a 20-40 mm and 40-80 mm fraction. It was found that smaller and larger waste was not sorted.

Among the optical sensors for CDW sorting, the project “Innovative solution for the separation of CDW” (CDW-recycling), funded by the LIFE+ programme, aimed to use innovative technologies to find solutions for CDW sorting (CDW-recycling project, 2016). In a first stage, the project designed and set up sorting processes for two fractions of CDW: 8-30 mm and 30-80 mm. To achieve this, currently used optical and blowing technologies from Pellenc Selective Technologies were adapted. In the second stage, the process was exported to and applied on an industrial-scale at the Nice-Saint Isidore site. This process demonstrates that it is possible to recover large quantities of CDW and with less of an environmental impact than using traditional CDW management techniques.

A variety of the latest optical-sensor technologies for CDW sorting were presented at the WG1 MINEA workshop. This information is included in the WBoA (Table 1):

- Technalia presented the results of two EU projects, namely IRCOW and HISER (Lisbona, 2016). The IRCOW project experimented with NIR sorting to remove contaminants (e.g. gypsum, organic material) from the stony particles of CDW (IRCOW project, 2014). The detected contaminants are separated by air jets. This mineral fraction was crushed, producing mixed recycled aggregates, which were additionally screened by means of UV-VIS inspection, which can separate the gray fractions (concrete) from the red ones (bricks and ceramic). Sorting capacities depend on the bulk density and grain size of the input fraction, but NIR sorting technology reached up to 11 ton/h/m (Bergmans et al., 2015). Results showed that organic material, gypsum and autoclaved aerated concrete can be significantly reduced or even eliminated during the NIR sorting treatment (Vegas et al., 2015).

HISER focused on Hiperspectral image (HIS) technologies for CDW sorting and developed a technology using Short-wave Infrared (SWIR). The main purpose of this technology was to close the cycle of grey fractions (concrete and plasters) and red fractions (ceramics and bricks) (Hollstein et al., 2016). A more recent study conducted by Hollstein et al. (2017) combined SWIR sensors with VIS-NIR for an on-line detection and sorting of gypsum and stony items with organic contamination in order to close the

recycling loops of gypsum, concrete and ceramic materials because of their exceptional potential for increasing sustainability by conserving construction resources. Results from this study showed that HSI technology can contribute to bringing down the economic threshold above which recycling is cost efficient. However, the industrial distribution of HSI in the CDW recycling field is currently insufficiently pronounced due to high investment costs.

- Zen Robotics used robots to sort a variety of CDW streams depending on their shapes and sizes, such as metals, different grades of wood, plastics and cardboard. This technology, which was presented in MINEA WG1 Workshop (Borkowsky, 2016), uses robots together with multiple accurate sensors (NIR; 3D; Hi-res RGB camera; Imaging metal detector and VIS) and self-learning software. Robots can also be trained to identify new types of waste and thus increase the efficiency of the process. In general, a Zen Robotics robot with two arms can make up to 4,000 picks per hour, making this technology one of the fastest waste sorting processes (around 10-20 t/h).

Figure 30. Functional principle of ZenRobotics (Zen Robotics, 2016)

Table 10 shows a summary of the existing and emerging technologies for CDW waste sorting.

Table 10. Synthesis of CDW waste sorting technologies and case studies

Tech	Case studies						Advantages	Limitations	Applied	Source
	CBC	G	W	AP	M	AB*				
Developed Technologies	Wet technologies						Higher quality of washed recycled products	Only for removal of low-density contaminants Needs sludge management and treatment	Germany and United Kingdom (CANDY project)	(CANDY project, 2014)
		✓	✓	✓	✓		Low cost Effective for sorting wood and organic waste from CDW	Only sorts two fractions: organic and others Needs sludge management and treatment Tested on a pilot-scale basis	Laboratory environment (Luleå University)	(MINEA Cost Action, 2016, Marklund, 2016)
	colour sorting + air	✓	✓	✓			Effectively used for wood, glass and gypsum removal Fast process (40 t/h)	Stony fractions and tiles can be further removed by density separation in a second stage	Germany	(Mulder et al., 2007, de Jong et al., 2005)
	DE X-ray	✓	✓	✓	✓		Effective for separation of organic and inorganic materials. In particular wood separation.	CDW fractions < 20 mm and >80 mm were not sorted. Low density, small or thin pieces are difficult to separate	Germany	(Mulder et al., 2007, Vrancken et al., 2017)
	NIR + UV-VIS	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	High-grade aggregates Low content of impurities in the output High speed sorting (11 ton/h)	Only for sorting grey and red fractions	Demolition project in Spain (IRCOW project)	(Bergmans et al., 2015, Vegas et al., 2015, IRCOW project, 2014, Lisbona, 2016)
	NIR + SWIR + UV-VIS	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Gypsum, Grey and red fractions can be sorted High-grade aggregates	High investment costs Dependency on material moisture	Demolition projects across 4 EU countries (HISER project)	(Hollstein et al., 2016, Hollstein et al., 2017, Lisbona, 2016)
Emerging Technologies	Optical + air blowing	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Recover large quantities of CDW in an industrial scale.	Suitable for fractions ranging between 8-80 mm	France (CDW-recycling project)	(CDW-recycling project, 2016)
	Robots	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Accurate sorting Fast process (10-20 t/h) Robots can be trained to identify new types of waste	High investment costs	Zen Robotics (ReWARD project)	(Zen Robotics, 2016, Borkowsky, 2016, MINEA Cost Action, 2016)
	Air jigging	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	The number of steps needed to recover concrete are reduced	Only for removal of low-density contaminants from stony fractions. Tested on a pilot-scale basis	Laboratory environment	(Ambros et al., 2017)

* Asbestos waste is collected and sorted manually on site.

Despite the relevant improvement in automatic CDW sorting technology which has been developed in the last seven years (Anding et al., 2011), more effort is still needed in order to optimize the ideal combination of traditional separation methods with further advanced automated sorting techniques. Furthermore, residential and other buildings are becoming more and more complex, leading to more complex CDW in the years ahead, and therefore requiring adapted advanced technologies for their recycling (Hollstein et al., 2016). Hence, the latest emerging technologies are focused on CDW detection by overlapping VIS, NIR and SWIR hyperspectral images in time and space in order to achieve a high grade recycled aggregate of good quality.

8 CASE STUDIES ON CONSTRUCTION AND DEMOLITION WASTE RECOVERY AND RECYCLING TECHNOLOGIES

This section provides a comprehensive overview of recycling and recovery technologies for the six case studies: concrete, bricks and ceramics; gypsum; wood; asphalt; metals; and asbestos.

8.1 Case study 1: concrete, bricks and ceramics waste recycling and recovery technologies

Concrete, bricks and ceramics (CBC) are the largest waste stream generated in CD activities. However, no recent data regarding CBC waste generation has been found. It is estimated that around 60-70% of total CDW is CBC waste (about 201-235 Mtonnes in 2014)¹⁰. Regarding the percentage of waste recovered, the only data for concrete waste was reported by Monier et al. (2011), in which it is stated that 75% of concrete waste was recovered for open loop recycling and 45% for closed loop recycling. Bricks and ceramics waste can be processed in the same recycling facilities as those designed for concrete recycling, which can treat all mineral waste coming from CDW. Depending on the typology of waste material, it is possible to shift among different working combinations to have the required grain size as output of the recycling process (Hiete, 2013).

The main processing recycling plants for CBC waste are stationary plants, which can process large amounts of waste, and mobile plants, which are designed for processing lower quantities of waste. The latter are very suitable for road construction and building demolition as they enable CBC waste to be processed on-site and the recycled aggregate to be reused directly on the same site. Additionally, crusher buckets are currently commercialized to reduce the particle size of the waste generated while dismantling a building (Figure 31).

Figure 31. Example of a crusher bucket (ANROSS LTD, 2017)

In general, CBC recycling procedures undergo the following stages (Hiete, 2013):

¹⁰ 336 Mtonnes of CDW (excluding excavations) were considered (2014) (see section 4.2.1)

- storing concrete waste;
- preliminary sieve to remove fine- grained fraction, including soil;
- manual or mechanical sorting to remove contaminants or unwanted materials such as wood, paper, plastics, etc.;
- removing ferrous metals using a magnet;
- reducing the size of materials with a crusher; and
- further sieving, shredding and mixing could also be performed in some cases if required.

Additionally, wet technologies have also been used for CBC recovery after removing ferrous metals with a magnet separator. For instance, Mlinar et al. (2016) presented such an onsite wet-screening technology for CBC recovery (Table 1) at the MINEA WG1 Workshop (MINEA Cost Action, 2016). This technology is based on a multi-stage wet screening process where water is circulated and continuously processed in the plant itself (Figure 32).

Figure 32. On-site wet classification technology for CBC waste (Mlinar, 2016)

Among recycling and recovery technologies exclusively for concrete waste, the following can be highlighted:

- Mulder et al. (2007) developed a treatment for concrete recycling based on the combination of thermal and mechanical energy. The procedure used a jaw crusher to reduce the size of the coarse concrete (below 10 cm); a magnet to remove any reinforcement steel, a rotary kiln for the combined input of thermal energy with temperatures below 700°C (to disintegrate the matrix) and mechanical energy (to further release the different concrete components); and finally, a vibrating screen and air separator to obtain coarse and fine aggregates and cement stone. The gravel and sand can be used as recovered aggregates, while the dehydrated cement stone fraction can be used as a substitute in the Portland cement production process.
- Lippiatt and Bourgeois (2012) investigated selective liberation of concrete's raw constituents for recycling by a combination of microwave heating and comminution.

They concluded that an efficient microwave-based process for concrete waste recycling requires the selection of comminution and separation technologies that can best reap the benefits of the mechanical changes produced by microwave heating. However, Akbarnezhad et al. (2011) reported that microwave heating alone only allowed partial liberation of aggregates from concrete samples, and thus an additional treatment, usually impact fragmentation, is needed for completing the concrete recycling process. In this sense, a further study combining both microwave heating and impact fragmentation was conducted by Bru et al. (2014) achieving significant reductions in energy consumption needed to fracture the concrete.

- Menard et al. (2013) compared electric impulse and microwave heating technologies in terms of quality of the output products (cement paste and aggregate). The electrical impulse was found to be less energy consuming than the microwave heating process (1-3 kWh/t compared to 10-40 kwh/t). Recently, Touze et al. (2017) assessed the feasibility of electro-fragmentation technology in terms of mechanical performance of concrete waste aggregate and as an integration tool to apply in the field of concrete recycling, confirming that the size of the aggregate and the nature of minerals can affect the mechanical performance of the aggregates.
- Moreover, Advanced Dry Recovery (ADR) technology uses kinetic energy to break the bonds that are formed by moisture and fine particles (de Vries et al., 2009). This technology was used in the EU C2CA project, aiming to turn demolition concrete into clean aggregates and cement (Delft University, 2011). The project applied an autogenous mill to increase the liberation of cement mortar from the surface of aggregates and ADR to remove the fines and light contaminants (Lotfi et al., 2014).

Recycling and recovery technologies for bricks and ceramic waste fragmentation were studied by the LIFE CERAM project, funded by EU Life+ programme. This project demonstrated the feasibility of achieving zero-waste in the ceramic tile manufacturing process through the manufacturing of a new product (LIFE CERAM project, 2016). This project used existing dry milling technologies (namely: hammer mills, plate mills and pendular mills) (Figure 33) and low- and high-powered granulation technologies (Figure 34) to process the ceramic waste (Quereda Vázquez et al., 2016).

(a) Hammer mill

(b) Plates mill

(c) Pendular mills

Figure 33. Dry milling technologies used in LIFE CERAM project (Quereda Vázquez et al., 2016)

(a) Low-powered granulator

(b) High-powered granulator

Figure 34. Granulation technologies used in LIFE CERAM project (Quereda Vázquez et al., 2016)

Table 11 shows a summary of the existing and emerging technologies for CBC waste recycling.

Table 11. Synthesis of waste recycling and recovery technologies for case study 1 (CBC)

	CBC	Advantages	Limitations	Applied	Source	
	c BC					
Developed Technologies	Thermal & mechanical	✓	Low cost	Multi stage process	Laboratory environment	(Mulder et al., 2007)
	MW heating	✓	Fast Less energy consumption	It is a pre-treatment. An additional method is needed to complete the recycling process.	Laboratory environment	(Akbarnezhad et al., 2011)
	MW heating + impact fragmentation	✓	Increase in the aggregate liberation	Higher energy consumption than electrodynamic fragmentation.	Laboratory environment	(Lippiatt and Bourgeois, 2012, Bru et al., 2014, Ménard et al., 2013)
Emerging Technologies	Dry mills & granulators	✓	Low cost	Applied to clean waste from tiles manufacturing process.	Tiles manufacturing plant in Spain (LIFE CERAM project)	(Quereda Vázquez et al., 2016, LIFE CERAM project, 2016)
	Electrodynamic fragmentation	✓	Low energy consumption	Can only be applied on samples in water leading	Demolition site in France (COFRAGE Project)	(Ménard et al., 2013, Touzé et al., 2017)
	Autogenous mill + ADR	✓	High-grade aggregate	High initial cost	Demolition project in the Netherlands (C2CA project)	(Lotfi et al., 2014, Delft University, 2011)

	CBC		Advantages	Limitations	Applied	Source
	c	BC				
Wet techs	✓	✓	On site and mobile plant Water is recovered in the same plant	Multi stage process	Bernegger company (Austria)	(Mlinar, 2016, MINEA Cost Action, 2016)

The outputs of CBC recovery and recycling technologies are mainly recycled aggregates. In general, the traditional recycling systems cannot guarantee sufficient quality of the recycled products to be of use in high-grade applications (Senaratne et al., 2017). However, multiple research studies have been conducted to analyse the feasibility of incorporating recycled aggregates in construction and building materials and applications.

The following recycled aggregates can be distinguished:

Concrete aggregates are suitable for different building and civil applications, such as in the manufacture of concrete or road sub-bases. The use of recycled aggregates cannot fully replace natural aggregates when concrete is used for structural purposes in construction (Jeffrey, 2011). At present, around 30% of recycled aggregate substitution is recommended in concrete used for structural applications (Etxeberria Larrañaga and Vegas, 2015).

Recycled aggregates resulting from bricks and ceramic waste are suitable for different low quality applications such as road sub-base construction and filling works rather than as aggregate substitutes in concrete (Jeffrey, 2011). In general, the presence of masonry and mortar in a concrete recycled aggregate can be detrimental in terms of physical, mechanical and chemical properties (Moriconi et al., 2003). However, recent studies have explored ways to improve the quality of bricks and ceramics in order to obtain recycled aggregate of such high quality that it could be used as concrete aggregate or as fine materials, such as sand or mortar coming from CDW recycling (Neno et al., 2014, Etxeberria Larrañaga and Vegas, 2015).

Cavalline et al. (2013) focused their attention on recycling red clay bricks as coarse aggregate fraction in order to replace natural aggregate in concrete production. Both studies compared the physical and mechanical properties of the recycled aggregates with their virgin equivalents, ensuring that these properties were kept similar in both samples. Furthermore, Moriconi et al. (2003) and Ledesma et al. (2015) investigated how fine aggregates (sand) can be replaced by waste containing both mortars and bricks, resulting in better bonding strength than the reference sample without waste. Results show that the fine aggregate substitution had a success rate of 50%.

Finally, recycled masonry mortars using recycled ceramic aggregates were also studied by Saiz Martínez et al. (2015) and Jiménez et al. (2013). Results showed that around 40% of the substitution ratio contributed to considerable boosting of some mechanical properties.

8.2 Case study 2: gypsum waste recycling and recovery technologies

Around 5 million tonnes of plasterboard waste was generated in the EU in 2011 and was reduced to around 1.9 million tonnes in 2013 (GtoG Project, 2013, Frost and Sullivan, 2011). Although gypsum products are indefinitely and fully recyclable, only 12.7% is currently recovered for closed loop recycling (GtoG Project, 2013).

The main research work carried out on end-of-life gypsum recycling technologies have focused on the recycling and recovery of plasterboards. Several European and American plasterboard manufacturers have implemented processing technologies to turn gypsum waste into usable raw materials (Pharos Project). For example, Gypsum Recycling International introduced the first patented mobile unit to transform gypsum waste recycling (Gypsum Recycling International, 2001). The next generation of units, such as XL recycling units, have greater capacity and were introduced in 2005 (Figure 35). The XL units consist of two trailers allowing them to be transported on a normal road in all countries without any special permit. With this technology it is possible to recycle plasterboard waste from newly built constructions as well as from demolition activities and, what's more, to treat plasterboard waste containing contaminants (screws, nails, wall paper etc.). In addition, the advancement of technologies to produce higher purity quality of gypsum powder from CDW plasterboard has enabled plants to use 25% of recycled powder in their mix of raw materials (Pharos Project).

Furthermore, McCamley (2003) patented a method and equipment for separating adhesive paper from paper-covered gypsum board. This method involves a magnet screening to automatically remove ferrous materials and employs a crusher to pulverize the waste into a screenable mixture of pieces of paper and gypsum particles. Then at least one screen is used to segregate the pieces of paper from the gypsum board particles. This technique may optionally also include a manual pre-sorting and removing non-gypsum materials from the gypsum board prior to pulverization, or may optionally also include additional screening steps.

Another patent from Rasmussen (2004) described a recycling apparatus for all kinds of products containing gypsum and, in particular, plasterboards. The technology comprises a coarse crusher, roller mill (where the coarse crushed material is rolled) and a perforated separating drum in which plasterboard waste is finally separated into a gypsum-free fraction and a reusable gypsum fraction.

Figure 35. Inputs, output and gypsum recycling XL unit (Gypsum Recycling International, 2005)

Likewise, Ahmed et al. (2011) used a technique comprising a crushing, screening and further thermal treatment (reaching temperatures of up to 140°C) to obtain basanite (hemi-hydrate calcium sulphite) to be used in an embankment construction project in the city of Ota, Japan, obtaining positive results in terms of soil stability and environmental effects. Similarly, Mitsubishi Materials developed a technology to recycle plasterboard waste as cement by firing it at high temperatures in cement kilns (Mitsubishi materials, 2017). This technology prevents the generation of hydrogen sulfide and other hazardous substances that were a concern during processing at landfills. In addition, waste plasterboard powder can substitute plaster to be added at the final stages of the cement production process, thereby also helping to achieve natural resource savings.

In addition, the Gy.eco project - funded by LIFE+ Programme and conducted in Italy - aimed to develop a protocol for the management and recovery of plasterboard waste. For this, a mobile waste treatment unit which can be moved from one recovery site to another was used, avoiding inactivity periods. This system is able to recycle up to 95% of gypsum waste from plasterboard scraps as new SRM for the production of mineral gypsum in industrial processes (Iscaro, 2015).

Similarly, the EU Gypsum to Gypsum (GtoG) project, which was presented at the WG1 MINEA Workshop, focused on plasterboard waste recovery in eight EU countries, namely: Belgium, France, Germany, Greece, Poland, Spain, the Netherlands and the UK (GtoG Project, 2013). In this project, gypsum waste was obtained with the crushing and sieving technologies used in different EU recycling plants and pre-drying operations before calcination (GtoG Project, 2015). Primary crushing was carried out using jaw crushers, roll crushers or impact crushers and, if needed, a secondary crushing was performed using hammermills. Finally, calcination was performed using kettle calciners, rotatory kilns and single-unit grinding and calcining equipment. Gypsum moisture was found to be a key factor affecting gypsum recycling.

Table 12 shows a summary of the gypsum recycling technologies and case studies. These technologies are mainly focused on plasterboards' waste processing rather than gypsum waste from interior coatings.

Table 12. Synthesis of waste recycling and recovery technologies for case study 2 (G)

Technology	Advantages	Limitations	Applied	Source	
Developed Techs	Magnet screening + dry crushing and sieving	Low cost	Slow process. Manual pre-sorting and second screening may be needed	Patents (McCamley, 2003, Rasmussen, 2004)	
	Screening, crushing + thermal treatment	Prevents the generation of hazardous substances	More than one phase process	Embankment construction project in Japan (Ahmed et al., 2011, Mitsubishi materials, 2017)	
	Automated sorting + dry crushing and screening	Compact and mobile unit Treats clean and contaminated plasterboards Fully automated (controls and sensors)	Protection of the weather conditions is essential	WRAP Gypsum Recycling International ^a (Pharos project)	(Gypsum Recycling International, 2005, WRAP, 2002, Pharos Project)
	Dry crushing and screening + preheating and calcination		protection against weather conditions is essential Purity of the gypsum waste is determinant	8 EU countries (GtoG project)	(GtoG Project, 2015)

Gypsum waste has traditionally been recycled following closed loop or open loop applications.

Regarding closed loop recycling, Rodríguez Orejón et al. (2014) incorporated crushed and burnt plasterboard waste in a gypsum matrix using two different particle sizes: fine and coarse. Despite the decrease in the mechanical strengths, an increase in the superficial hardness was observed when 5% of coarse plasterboard waste was incorporated. This composite complies with the minimum values required by the regulation for gypsum composites and can therefore be applied as renders and plasters, both horizontally and vertically, and also for the manufacture of prefabricated elements. In addition, the GtoG project developed recycled gypsum plasterboards (containing gypsum waste from both production and CDW) with similar performance to Type A plasterboards. Plasterboards were manufactured in 5 different manufacturing gypsum plants, but only two of them successfully incorporated 30% of gypsum waste. However, 25% of recycled gypsum was successfully incorporated into the five plants examined without any permanent investment in equipment and infrastructure from the manufacturers' side. The following limitations to further increase the percentage of gypsum waste were:

- limitation of the production process, and thus modifications, in terms of additives and equipment, are needed when using gypsum waste becomes standard practice;

- the amount of residual paper and fibre content of recycled gypsum should be kept < 1%; and
- the purity of the gypsum waste and moisture content are determinant to reach higher percentages of waste incorporation;

Regarding open loop recycling, gypsum waste can be used as a bulking agent to absorb moisture excess or odours, or it can be added to the soil as an amendment (Long, 1978, Ahmed et al., 2011, Mitsubishi materials, 2017). Gypsum waste from building activities can be recycled into different applications for the construction industry. Ganjian et al. (2008) combined gypsum waste (mainly coming from plasterboard) and other by-products to form a novel binder that has high potential to stabilize the layer of soils beneath road construction as a source of sulphate to form a “sulphate activated pozzolana”. This solution, however, makes gypsum unavailable for further recycling loops.

8.3 Case study 3: wood waste recycling and recovery technologies

The data available leads to an estimation of CD wood waste generation in the EU of between 10 to 20 million tonnes per year, out of which only 25% to 50% is recycled for particle boards manufacture and 34% for energy recovery (Monier et al., 2011). The source of CD wood waste generation varies in line with CD activities. Construction activities generate off-cuts from structural woods, wood packaging, scaffolding and wooden hoardings (Pigorsch et al., 2014), while demolition activities produce used structural timbers, wooden floorboards, joists, beams, staircases and doors (Morales Conde et al., 2016). Wood from CDW is often contaminated (covered by glues, resins, plastics, etc.) and mixed with other waste flows. Some of these substances exhibit high levels of toxic contaminants and therefore a more complex recycling procedure is needed.

Mechanical technologies have been developed to recycle wood waste not containing toxic contaminants. For instance, Tokyo Mokosho Company (2011) developed a technology for wood waste processing under the “Recycling of Waste Wood and Waste Plastics into Recycled Plywood” project in 2004. This process unfolded in the following phases:

- preliminary crushing: wood waste (or even plywood) is crushed into wood chips around 30-50 mm in size;
- removal of contaminants: this separation process is done through magnetic separators that allow the removal of metals, improving the quality of the recycled wood produced;
- additional crushing: sorted wood is crushed into smaller chips and finally processed by a delimitator into wood fibers; and
- finally, the wood waste can be grounded to a fine dust.

However, a very clean supply of wood waste feedstock is needed. For this reason the material has to be highly separated (Defra, 2012). Two main problems arising with this technology relate

to high investment costs for a hammer mill and the potentially explosive nature of the material (Buehlmann, 2002).

McMahon et al. (2008) developed an alternative method consisting of a composting procedure and resulting in a feasible alternative to manage wood from CDW. This study analysed three compost mixes using a mix of shredded chip board, medium density fibre, hardboard and melamine together with three nutrient supplements: poultry manure, eco-bio mixture and green waste. The results showed that high quality compost can be obtained from composting mixed board product wood waste, making it suitable for a variety of applications.

Furthermore, a recent spin-out company from the Imperial College, named Chrysalix Technologies, has developed a chemical process using low-cost ionic liquids for wood recycling (Chrysalix technologies, 2017). This low-temperature procedure (below 200°C) separates the cellulose and lignin, and no emissions are released during the process as the ionic liquids have low vapour pressure. This procedure is a pre-treatment technology which is compatible with metal and organic contaminants like paint and preservatives.

Two recently EU-funded projects which deal with wood waste recycling are BioReg (2017) and WRING (2016). In particular, WRING project aims to enhance wood recyclability by developing innovative contaminants' detection and removal technologies as well as sorting and reprocessing systems (WRING project, 2016).

Moreover, specific techniques aimed to remove toxic substances from wood waste have been researched for many years (Helsen and Van den Bulck, 2005). Among the technologies and case studies dealing with wood contaminated with toxic substances, the following can be highlighted:

- Mechanical, chemical and microbial methods have been used to eliminate chromated copper arsenate (CCA) from wood waste (Clausen, 2000, McMahon et al., 2008).
- Wang et al. (2016) used a magnesia cement and CO₂ curing process to transform contaminated wood waste into eco-friendly cement-bonded particleboards. This technology, compared to other techniques for the production of traditional cement, reaches lower temperatures during the process, thus reducing energy consumption. Results demonstrated acceptable compatibility between the compounds and value-added properties of the final product.
- Rautkoski et al. (2016) presented a case study in which chemical and thermo-mechanical pulping, as well as mechanical milling, were used for pulping contaminated wood waste chips received from a construction waste treatment plant. Despite the fact that wood contaminated with copper must meet specific requirements to be recovered, no other technical limits were found during the work. The resulting output can serve as SRM for fibre-based products.

Table 13 shows a summary of technologies and case studies for wood waste recycling. In general, the recycling process in wood recycling plants is increasing in efficiency and cost-effectiveness.

Table 13. Synthesis of waste recycling and recovery technologies for case study 3 (W)

	Main features	Applied	Advantages	Limitations	Source
Developed Techs	Mechanical sieving and crushing + magnetic separation	Japan ^a	Quality of output material	High investment costs	(Tokyo Mokka-sho, 2011, Buehlmann, 2002, Defra, 2012)
	Composting	United Kingdom	Low cost Low energy consumption	Moisture content is critical for the technique	(McMahon et al., 2008)
Emerging Technologies	Magnesia cement and CO ₂ curing *	Lab tests in Hong Kong	Low energy consumption	Preliminary screening and shredding is needed. For cement-bonded particleboard manufacture	(Wang et al., 2016)
	Chemical and thermo-mechanical process *	Lab tests	Quality of output material	Wood contaminated with copper requires specific process.	(Rautkoski et al., 2016)
	Ionic liquids	United Kingdom	Low-cost No emissions are released	Is a pre-treatment	(Chrysalix technologies, 2017)

^a Under the "Recycling of Waste Wood and Waste Plastics into Recycled Plywood" project.

* Technology for wood waste contaminated with toxic substances

Wood waste output is sorted according to its grade. Four different grades are distinguished according to its general suitability for certain end uses (WRAP, 2012, Environment Agency, 2014):

- Grade A: "Clean" recycled wood output, used for high value markets such as animal bedding and panel products.
- Grade B: may contain Grade A wood together with other waste wood sourced from CD activities. It can be used in panel products and incinerations complying with Directive 2000/76/EC.
- Grade C: must be managed by incinerations complying with Directive 2000/76/EC
- Grade D: is hazardous wood waste and it is only suitable for special landfill or incinerations complying with Directive 2000/76/EC.

Therefore, when toxic contaminants are present in the wood waste (Grade D), it can only be incinerated. If the wood is clean, it is suitable for close loop and open loop recycling. In terms of close loop recycling, clean wood waste can be used for wood-based panel manufacture mainly for insulation purposes, which are known as Oriented Strand Boards (OSB). OSB production is possible only if some parameters are limited, there is the right mixture of softwood and hardwood, a suitable porosity and an absence of nails or metals (Jeffrey, 2011, Hubbe, 2014). Examples for open loop recycling include: the production of pellets for indoor heating, biomass energy generation; animal bedding; or for porous and sealed surface applications.

8.4 Case study 4: asphalt waste recycling and recovery technologies

Approximately 50 million tons of asphalt waste is generated in the EU each year, with over 70% of it being reused for pavement surfaces (Kara et al., 2017), a figure rising to 80%, for instance, in the case of Germany (Monier et al., 2011).

The following asphalt recycling technologies can be highlighted, depending on the method chosen to rehabilitate the road (Tam and Tam, 2006, Gallivan, 2018): (1) Cold planing, (2) Heat-transfer method, (3) Cold recycling methods and (4) Full Depth Reclamation.

1. Cold planing uses front mechanical milling machines for removing existing pavement and for preparing the surface for repaving. The milling equipment has a large diameter rotary cutting drum (with replaceable cutting teeth) and water is sprayed during the milling process to control the amount of dust generated (Hadžikadić and Avdaković, 2017). Most mills are equipped with automatic grade control systems to mill to the specified elevations and grades.
2. The heat-transfer method is used for hot recycling procedures to help mix recycled asphalt aggregates with natural aggregates. In this method, the moisture content in recycled asphalt aggregates needs to be controlled in order to achieve a good production rate. Two types of hot recycling can be distinguished, depending on whether the recycling process is done on site (Hot in-place recycling - HIR) or in a fixed plant (Hot plant recycling - HPR). The latter uses a continuous fixed mixing plant with integrated drum-mix or double barrel dryers-mixers (Sivilevičius et al., 2017). HIR is the most common technique and uses a recycling train containing a heater unit. Multiple heaters and pre-heater units are currently available on the market, i.e. hot air, microwave, infrared or radiant heat (Watson, 2011).

Figure 36. Example of front milling machine (left) and HIR train REMIXER 4500 (right) (WIRTGEN, 2017)

In general, there are multiple technologies readily available for production of 100% recycled hot mix asphalt (Zaumanis et al., 2014, Zaumanis et al., 2016). All of them

use indirect heating methods as they cause less hydrocarbon vapors and odours than direct heating (Volker Wessels, 2013):

- RapSaver is a preheating system comprised of a continuously fed sealed conductive heating system, allowing the waste to be heated and dried using a slow moving hollow screw heating auger (Misajet, 2007).
 - In the Highly Ecological Recycling Asphalt (HERA) System - installed in the Asphaltcentrale Rotterdam Asphalt Plant - hot gasses heat the outside of the drum, thus heating and drying the asphalt while rotating (Volker Wessels, 2013).
 - Cyclean system is a microwave heating technology which has limited use as it demands higher energy consumption than other conventional systems (Zaumanis et al., 2014).
 - Ammann RAH 100 is a counter flow dryer with a two phase drum where the waste is heated with hot air and dispatched before contact with direct flame (Zaumanis et al., 2016).
3. Cold recycling consists of recycling asphalt pavement without the application of heat during the recycling process to produce a rehabilitated pavement. As for the hot recycling, cold recycling can be divided into two categories: in-place (CIR) or central-plant (CCPR). There are also no emissions with this method but it is half the cost of hot in-place recycling and the materials are 100% recycled (Tam and Tam, 2006).
- CIP recycling: there are different types of CIR recycling train configurations, depending on how the asphalt waste is collected and sieved, how the additives are added, mixed and controlled and how the final mix is placed (Dunn and Cross, 2001). However, these technologies generally comprise the following phases: mix tank, milling unit (sometimes a crusher and a screen), asphalt paver and a combination of pneumatic and vibratory rollers (Stroup-Gardiner, 2011).
 - CCPR recycling: is the same as CIR, but takes the asphalt waste to a plant off site where it is mixed and brought back to the site. As the waste needs to be transported to the plant, there are some additional costs (CONEXPO, 2017).

Figure 37. Example of CIR recycling train. (County Government, 2017)

4. Full Depth Reclamation (FDR) is used to rehabilitate the full thickness of the asphalt pavement and underlying materials and is performed on the roadway without the addition of heat, similar to CIR technology. FDR equipment is not as long as either a HIR or a CIR technology, but consists of a series of units: a reclaimer unit, stabilizing additive unit/s, motor grader, and rollers (Dunn and Cross, 2001, Bocci et al., 2014).

Figure 38. Example of FDR recycling train (CNCA, 2017)

Table 14. Synthesis of waste recycling and recovery technologies - case study 4 (AP)

Technology	Advantages	Limitations	Source
Developed Techs	Cold planning	Small machine. Low cost Minimum traffic interruptions	A preliminary preparation of the surface is recommended. (Hadžikadić and Avdaković, 2017)
	Heat-transfer	Better performance of resulting pavements	Higher emissions. Moister content needs to be controlled. Uses a larger machine (Sivilevičius et al., 2017) (Volker Wessels, 2013) (Zaumanis et al., 2014) (Zaumanis et al., 2016, Karlsson and Isacsson, 2006)
	Cold recycling	No emissions Low cost	Is affected by the climate conditions. Uses a larger machine. (Tam and Tam, 2006) (Stroup-Gardiner, 2011) (CONEXPO, 2017)
	Full Depth Reclamation	Greater depth of cut. Small equipment	Higher initial cost (Dunn and Cross, 2001, Bocci et al., 2014).

Asphalt waste is crushed forming asphalt aggregates which are usually bonded with cement or a bituminous emulsion to replace the sand or cement sub-bases (Tam and Tam, 2006). In addition to these binders, asphalt aggregate can also be stabilized with blast furnace slag, fine slag or motor oil (Oliveira et al., 2013).

8.5 Case study 5: metals waste recycling and recovery technologies

Among the different kinds of metals consumed, steel is one of the most frequently used in the construction sector.

The current steel recovery processes consist of remanufacturing, reuse and recycling. Most steel products used in construction are already remanufactured or reused. Steel scraps are recovered with good quality steel products for direct re-use and the rest are destined for recycling in steelworks.

In general, the steel waste collection process includes the following stages:

- disassembling of large steel components, which are dismantled and often sheered, while small parts are picked up using magnets or automatic methods;
- waste is collected on special scrap yards, where the level of radiation is checked before admittance;
- the unprocessed scrap is dragged to infeed conveyors (second radiation detector) and processed through special hammer mills;
- fist-sized shredded scrap falls afterwards to a shaker table and conveyor below. these pieces are composed of ferrous, non-ferrous metal and non-metallic material. Shredded scrap goes through another radiation detector just before the sorting process starts;
- using electrical currents, high-pressure air flows and liquid floating systems, pieces are separated and the ferrous material recovery is almost completed;
- the final stage includes manual selection of ferrous material in order to ensure the purity of recycled steel; and
- the selected steel goes then through secondary processors (often scrap brokers) or steel mills where it is prepared for transportation to steel production plants.

Metal detectors and separators are widely used for removal of steel from a mixed feed and provide a reliable and low cost method for enhanced metal recovery or removal. Mesina et al. (2003) described an electromagnetic sensor for separating steel from mixed non-ferrous metals.

The X-ray transmission method depends upon the density and the thickness of the target metal fraction (Ramachandra, 2006). Similarly, the dual energy X-ray transmission (DE-XRT) is a modified version of the X-ray transmission technique (Gundupalli et al., 2017), which is an effective method for sorting materials based on differences in atomic number. It can be applied for sorting pure components or composed particles (such as aluminium with a steel screw or other mechanically connected metal particles) (De Jong et al., 2003, Mesina et al., 2007). A more recent study combined electromagnetic and DE-XRT sensors, providing a relatively low cost sensing technology without the need for pre-treatment (Mesina et al., 2007).

Grzegorzek et al. (2011) described a system in which a Laser Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy (LIBS) was fixed over the conveyor system to obtain data. It had a camera and a line laser for sensing metals. Machine learning algorithms were used to classify materials based on their characteristic spectral emission signatures. Despite the good accuracy in separating materials, this technique can only be used for waste streams not containing lubricants, paints or oxide layers (Gesing and Harbeck, 2008, Gundupalli et al., 2017).

Huang et al. (2011) combined a 3D color scan camera with a laser beam attached to the conveyor belt in order to sort the waste by shape and color. When using this method, an accuracy of around 98% can be achieved for non-ferrous metals (Huang et al., 2010).

Once the different metal fractions are separated, the following technologies can be used to produce recycled steel (Fenton, 2003, Proctor et al., 2000, Brimacombe et al., 2005, World steel association, 2011):

- Primary steel production refers to the manufacture of iron (hot metal) from iron ore (converted into iron slag) in a Blast Furnace (BF) and subsequently processed in the BOF (Basic Oxygen Furnace) to make steel slag. Although the BOF method is mainly used for the production of iron, recycling is also possible with this process when the amount of waste added is small. Usually BOF uses 10-20% of scrap steel to make new steel.
- Secondary steel production, known as Electric Arc Furnace (EAF), converts scraps into new steel by re-melting old steel as steel slag. EAF steelmaking uses almost 100% recycled steel, which contains greater concentrations of residual elements. This steel is used to make structural beams, plates, reinforcing bars and other products that require little cold working.

Table 15. Synthesis of waste recycling and recovery technologies - case study 5 (M)

Technology	Advantages	Limitations	Applied	Source	
Developed Techs	ENS	Pre-processing is not necessary	S+ S Metallsuchgerate Recyclingtechnik GmbH The Netherlands	(Mesina et al., 2003)	
		Not sensitive to dust, coatings or other impurities			
	Sorting	DE-XRT	(depends on density and thickness of the metal fraction)	Laboratory environment	(De Jong et al., 2003, Mesina et al., 2007)
		EMS + DE-XRT	Pre-processing is not necessary Low cost	Laboratory environment	(Mesina et al., 2007)
		3D camera + laser	98% can be achieved for non-ferrous metals	Laboratory environment	(Huang et al., 2010)
LIBS	Good results for copper and brass separation	Not suitable for waste containing lubricants, paints or oxide	Laboratory environment	(Gesing and Harbeck, 2008, Gundupalli et al., 2017, Grzegorzek et al., 2011)	
Re-melting	BF + BOF	is self-sufficient in energy	Widely used worldwide	(Fenton, 2003, Proctor et al., 2000, Brimacombe et al., 2005, World steel association, 2011)	
	EAF	100% recycled steel			
		Up to 20% of waste High energy consumption and CO ₂ emissions			
		Amount of zinc needs to be controlled. Dust cannot be dumped because of environmental regulations - higher cost			

8.6 Case study 6: asbestos waste recycling and recovery technologies

No statistics about demolition asbestos waste (quantities and destinations) in the EU are available because asbestos waste is not generated anymore as asbestos has been banned since January 2005 (Monier et al., 2011).

Nowadays asbestos waste can be recycled and recovered through remediation and used for the production of SRM. Although the process of inertization of asbestos by means of recrystallization at high temperature has been known for about 30 years, only in a few cases can the process be applied on large-scale industrial plants. One such example is the INERTAM-Europlasma industrial plant in Morcenx (France), which has been active since 1999. It uses a plasma torch system for the vitrification of asbestos, containing materials at high temperature (around 1600°C). This technology is energy intensive and expensive and is therefore not widespread in all other countries (Hiete, 2013).

In the context of examining techniques for asbestos recovery, Plescia et al. (2003) presented a study that focuses on the mechano-chemical transformation of some waste containing asbestos. A high-speed mill was used to simulate the operating conditions of a mechano-

chemical reactor. Results revealed a complete alteration of asbestos fiber, which was brought about by a mechano-chemical transformation which makes chrysotile fiber tend towards an amorphous phase. The results obtained are promising from an environmental and economic point of view, as it indicates that the process can be used in small recycling plants or mobile units.

Leonelli et al. (2006) studied the possibility of transforming asbestos into non-hazardous silicate by means of microwave thermal treatment. The work indicates that the asbestos fiber follows an inertization process. In addition, the output material can also be recycled in porcelain stoneware tiles and ceramic bricks without any significant variation in terms of physical properties for these products. Furthermore, this process seems to be 10 times less expensive than disposal as toxic waste. Similarly, the latest European funded projects dealing with amiantos' recovery, namely AMIANTE and IRCOW, are also focused on Microwave Thermal Treatment. The AMIANTE project (2014) built an efficient microwave reactor in which a neutralization process of asbestos waste was carried out. Another important objective of the AMIANTE program was checking the material after the microwave process. The material after the process, called ATONIT, is neutral for the natural environment and can be used:

- As an aggregate for road construction.
- As an insulating layer in the construction of landfills.
- As an additive for concrete.

Finally, the IRCOW project (IRCOW project, 2014) developed an on-site microwave energy thermal treatment which allows the disintegration of asbestos and other mineral fibres.

Regarding asbestos recycling techniques, Viani and Gualtieri (2013) investigated a thermal treatment for recycling Cement-Asbestos as Calcium sulfoaluminate clinker. The latter is a novel cement binder designed to reduce CO₂ emissions. Results show that up to 29% was successfully introduced in a raw material mix, producing different clinker samples at two temperatures: 1250°C and 1300°C.

Colangelo et al. (2011) investigated a process that is able to eliminate hazardous fiber of the Cement-Asbestos. The Cement-Asbestos is milled by means of a high-energy ring mill for up to 4 hours. The technological efficacy of the recycling process is evaluated by preparing and heating hydraulic lime and milled powder-based mortar. The test shows a good response in terms of hydration kinetics and the mechanical properties of the treated Cement-Asbestos.

Table 16. Synthesis of waste recycling and recovery technologies for case study 6 (AB)

	Main features	Advantages	Limitations	Applied	Source
Developed Techs	Plasma torch system	-	High temperatures needed. High energy consumption High cost	INERTAM-Europlasma industrial plant in Morcenx (France)	(Hiete, 2013)
	Mechano-chemical treatment	reduced gas and dust emissions Small and mobile units	Prototype scale	Laboratory environment	(Plescia et al., 2003)
	Microwave thermal treatment	Low cost	Prototype scale	Laboratory environment	(Leonelli et al., 2006)
	High-energy ring mill	Efficient	For cement waste containing asbestos	Laboratory environment	(Colangelo et al., 2011)
Emerging Techs	Thermal treatment	Less CO ₂ emissions	For cement waste containing asbestos	Laboratory environment	(Viani and Gualtieri, 2013)
	Microwave thermal treatment + final control	Low cost Mobile unit	- -	AMIANTE project IRCOW project	(AMIANTE project, 2014) (IRCOW project, 2014)

Figure 39. shows a summary of developed and emerging technologies used for sorting and processing the selected six case studies in this report.

Figure 39. Summary of CDW recovery and recycling technologies and outputs for each case study

9 RECOMMENDATIONS FOR IMPROVING CONSTRUCTION AND DEMOLITION WASTE MANAGEMENT RECOVERY AND RECYCLING

The following recommendations are suggested in Table 17 for the European Union and MS. These recommendations have been summarized in 4 main topics to address existing barriers to CDW recovery and recycling: (1) Legislative, (2) Data quality and harmonization, (3) Improved reverse logistics and (4) Market readiness for secondary materials.

Table 17. Recommendations for improving CDW recovery and recycling

LEGISLATIVE

- Development of specific national regulation for CDW management
- Greater policy enforcement and control
- Efficient economic incentives (penalties and bans) to help prevent that landfilling is the cheapest option for waste management

DATA QUALITY AND HARMONIZATION

- Harmonisation of CDW definitions and waste stream classifications (EWL and ELW)
- Improved data collection and real-time reporting methods.
- Common methods for measuring the overall performance of each MS.
- Create transparency and credibility for stakeholders.
- Detailed information in terms of types and capacities of CDW management facilities in order to determine future requirements
- Standardization of technical data of recycled materials
- Development of code systems for material recognition

IMPROVED REVERSE LOGISTICS

- Effective CDW collection and monitoring
- Development and use of innovative tracking systems
- Greater number and better distribution of CDW management facilities
- Improve cross-border coordination between regions

MARKET READINESS FOR SECONDARY MATERIALS

- Achieve purity of the waste input
- Assure a well-functioning on-site separation
- Improve workers' knowledge and training
- Set minimum quality specifications for waste inputs and harmonise them across MS (when possible)
- Guarantee the supply of long-term feedstock
- Optimised CDW sorting and recovering technologies
- Greater economic and other incentives for using recycled products
- Assure the quality of recycled products
- Standardization of minimum technical specifications for recycled products across all MS

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References

- AHMED, A., UGAI, K. & KAMEI, T. 2011. *Laboratory and field evaluations of recycled gypsum as a stabilizer agent in embankment construction. Soils and foundations, 51, 975-990.*
- AKBARNEZHAD, A., ONG, K., ZHANG, M., TAM, C. & FOO, T. 2011. *Microwave-assisted beneficiation of recycled concrete aggregates. Construction and Building Materials, 25, 3469-3479.*
- AL-SALEM, S., LETTIERI, P. & BAEYENS, J. 2009. *Recycling and recovery routes of plastic solid waste (PSW): A review. Waste Management, 29, 2625-2643.*
- AMBROS, W. M., SAMPAIO, C. H., CAZACLIU, B. G., MILTZAREK, G. L. & MIRANDA, L. R. 2017. *Usage of air jigging for multi-component separation of construction and demolition waste. Waste Management, 60, 75-83.*
- AMIANTE PROJECT. 2014. *The development of selected hazardous wastes utilization technologies, based on microwave thermal treatment (MTT) method. Project ID: 222142 Funded under: FP7-SME [Online]. Available: www.amiante.pl [Accessed January 2018].*
- ANROSS LTD. 2017. *"Crusha" Buckets. Anross Excavator Attachments [Online]. United Kingdom. Available: <http://www.anross.co.uk/products/crusha.html> [Accessed January 2018].*
- ARM, M., WIK, O., ENGELSEN, C. J., ERLANDSSON, M., HJELMAR, O. & WAHLSTRÖM, M. 2017. *How Does the European Recovery Target for Construction & Demolition Waste Affect Resource Management? Waste and Biomass Valorization, 8, 1491-1504.*
- BARTELINGS, H., VAN BEUKERING, P., KUIK, O., LINDERHOF, V., OOSTERHUIS, F., BRANDER, L. & WAGTENDONK, A. 2005. *Effectiveness of landfill taxation. The Netherlands.*
- BERGMANS, J., BROOS, K., NIELSEN, P., DIERCKX, P., BRIJSSE, Y. & JACOBS, K. 2015. *Recycling of construction and demolition waste: case study in the Port of Antwerp. Proc. ISWA, 7-9.*
- BIOREG PROJECT. 2017. *Absorbing the Potential of Wood Waste in EU Regions and Industrial Bio-based Ecosystems (BIOREG) project. Horizon 2020 project ID: 727958 [Online]. Available: http://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/206094_en.html [Accessed January 2018].*
- BOCCI, M., GRILLI, A., CARDONE, F. & FERROTTI, G. 2014. *Full-depth reclamation for the rehabilitation of local roads: a case study. International Journal of Pavement Engineering, 15, 191-201.*

- BORKOWSKY, M. Year. Zenrobotics waste sorting technologies. In: ACTION, M. C., ed. Workshop "Recovery technologies for construction and demolition waste" 16-17 November 2016 2016 Vienna.
- BRIMACOMBE, L., COLEMAN, N. & HONESS, C. 2005. Recycling, reuse and the sustainability of steel. MilleniumSteel International.
- BRU, K., TOUZÉ, S., BOURGEOIS, F., LIPPIATT, N. & MÉNARD, Y. 2014. Assessment of a microwave-assisted recycling process for the recovery of high-quality aggregates from concrete waste. *International Journal of Mineral Processing*, 126, 90-98.
- BUEHLMANN, U. 2002. Value-added opportunities for recycled wood. *Recycling woods: a supplement to recycling works*, 01-04.
- CANDY PROJECT. 2014. CompAct highly mobile Next generation construction, Demolition and excavation waste recoverY system. Know-how. [Online]. Available: <https://www.cdeglobal.com/media/4570/fees-candy-project-quarry-management-en.pdf> [Accessed January 2018].
- CAPEL, C. 2008a. Waste shredding: An important precursor for efficient sorting [Online]. Available: <https://waste-management-world.com/a/waste-shredding-an-important-precursor-for-efficient-sorting> [Accessed December 2017].
- CAPEL, C. 2008b. Waste sorting: A look at the separation and sorting techniques in today's European market [Online]. Available: <https://waste-management-world.com/a/waste-sorting-a-look-at-the-separation-and-sorting-techniques-in-todayrsquos-european-market> [Accessed December 2017].
- CAVALLINE, T. L. & WEGGEL, D. C. 2013. Recycled brick masonry aggregate concrete: Use of brick masonry from construction and demolition waste as recycled aggregate in concrete. *Structural survey*, 31, 160-180.
- CDW-RECYCLING PROJECT. 2016. CDW-recycling - Innovative solution for the separation of construction and demolition waste LIFE11 ENV/FR/000752 [Online]. Available: http://ec.europa.eu/environment/life/project/Projects/index.cfm?fuseaction=search.ds_pPage&n_proj_id=4187&docType=pdf [Accessed January 2018].
- CEWEP. 2017. Landfill tax and bans for EU Member States [Online]. Available: <http://www.cewep.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/12/Landfill-taxes-and-bans-overview.pdf> [Accessed January 2018].
- CLAUSEN, C. A. 2000. CCA removal from treated wood using a dual remediation process. *Waste Management and Research*, 18, 485-488.
- CNCA. 2017. California Nevada Cement Association. Pavement Recycling (FDR) & CTB [Online]. Available: <http://cncement.org/portfolio-item/pavement-recycling/> [Accessed January 2018].

- COLANGELO, F., CIOFFI, R., LAVORGNA, M., VERDOLOTTI, L. & DE STEFANO, L. 2011. *Treatment and recycling of asbestos-cement containing waste. Journal of hazardous materials*, 195, 391-397.
- CONEXPO. 2017. *Requirements for Successful Asphalt Pavement Recycling [Online]. Las Vegas. Available: <http://www.conexpoconagg.com/news/june-2017/requirements-for-successful-asphalt-pavement-recyc/> [Accessed January 2018].*
- COUNTY GOVERNMENT. 2017. *Cold In-Place Recycling (CIR) [Online]. Available: <http://dpw.lacounty.gov/qmed/lacroads/TreatmentColdinPlace.aspx> [Accessed January 2018].*
- CHEN, Y.-S., HSIAU, S.-S., LEE, H.-Y., CHYOU, Y.-P. & HSU, C.-J. 2010. *Size separation of particulates in a trommel screen system. Chemical Engineering and Processing: Process Intensification*, 49, 1214-1221.
- CHRYSALIX TECHNOLOGIES. 2017. *Chrysalix Technologies [Online]. United Kingdom. Available: <http://www.chrysalixtechnologies.com/> [Accessed January 2018].*
- DE JONG, T., DALMIJN, W. & KATTENTIDT, H. 2003. *Dual energy X-ray transmission imaging for concentration and control of solids. Proc. 22nd Int. Min. Proc. Cong. IMPC-2003.*
- DE JONG, T., FABRIZI, L. & KUILMAN, W. 2005. *Dry density separation of mixed construction and demolition waste, presentation for the 2005 Sortierkolloquium. TU Berlin.*
- DE VRIES, W., REM, P. & BERKHOUT, P. Year. *ADR: a new method for dry classification. In: Proceedings of the ISWA international conference, 2009. 103-113.*
- DEFRA 2012. *Wood waste: A short review of recent research. London: Department for Environment Food and Rural Affairs.*
- DEILMANN, C., SCHILLER, G., GRUHLER, K. & ORTLEPP, R. Year. *Material Flow Analysis of stocks and flows to assess CDW recovery potential. In: ACTION, M. C., ed. Workshop "Recovery technologies for construction and demolition waste" 16-17 November 2016 2016 Vienna.*
- DELFT UNIVERSITY. 2011. *C2CA project [Online]. Available: <http://www.c2ca.eu/> [Accessed January 2018].*
- DELOITTE 2015a. *Construction and Demolition Waste Management in Poland.*
- DELOITTE 2015b. *Screening template for Construction and Demolition Waste management in The Netherlands.*

- DELOITTE 2016. Workshop “Improving management of construction and demolition waste”. Background paper within the framework of the project ‘Resource efficient use of mixed waste’ Brussels: European Commission
- DODBIBA, G. & FUJITA, T. 2004. Progress in separating plastic materials for recycling. *Physical Separation in Science and Engineering*, 13, 165-182.
- DUNN, L. & CROSS, S. 2001. *Basic asphalt recycling manual*. Annapolis, Md. Asphalt recycling and reclaiming association (ARRA).
- EDMUND OPTICS. 2017. What is SWIR? [Online]. Available: <https://www.edmundoptics.com/resources/application-notes/imaging/what-is-swir/> [Accessed January 2018].
- EEA 2016. *Environmental taxation and EU environmental policies*. Office of the European Union. Luxembourg: European Environment Agency.
- ENVIRONMENT AGENCY. 2014. *Briefing on Regulation of Wood. Our approach to working with the wood recycling sector on the management of waste wood* [Online]. United Kingdom. Available: https://consult.environment-agency.gov.uk/psc/st21-6ju-mr-robert-ainsworth-mrs-anne-ainsworth/supporting_documents/4.%20Briefing%20on%20Regulation%20of%20Wood.pdf [Accessed January 2018].
- ETTLINGER, S. & BAPASOLA, A. 2016. *Landfill Tax, Incineration Tax and Landfill Ban in Austria*. Eunomia and the Institute for European Environmental Policy for the DG Environment of the European Commission.
- ETXEBERRIA LARRAÑAGA, M. & VEGAS, I. 2015. Effect of fine ceramic recycled aggregate (RA) and mixed fine RA on hardened properties of concrete. *Magazine of concrete research*, 67, 645-655.
- EUR-LEX. 2017. *National transposition measures communicated by the Member States concerning: Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 November 2008 on waste and repealing certain Directives (Text with EEA relevance)* [Online]. Available: <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/NIM/?uri=CELEX:32008L0098> [Accessed December 2017].
- EUROPEAN COMMISSION 2016. *EU Construction & Demolition Waste Management Protocol*. Brussels: European Commission. Directorate-General for Internal market, Industry.
- EUROPEAN COMMISSION 2010. *Environmental statistics and accounts in Europe*. Publications Office of the European Union. Luxembourg: Eurostat.
- EUROPEAN COMMISSION 2011. *Supporting Environmentally Sound Decisions for Construction and Demolition (C&D) Waste Management. A practical guide to Life Cycle Thinking (LCT) and Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)*.

EUROPEAN COMMISSION 2012. *Preparing a Waste Management Plan - A methodological guidance note Luxembourg: DG Environment.*

EUROPEAN COMMISSION 2013. *Detailed assessment of Waste Management Plans - First batch ENV.C.2/FRA/2013/0023. Luxembourg: DG Environment.*

EUROPEAN COMMISSION 2015. *Proposal for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Directive 2008/98/EC on waste. Official Journal of the European Union.*

EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT 1999. *Council Directive 1999/31/EC of April 1999 on the landfill of waste. L. Official Journal of the European Communities.*

EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT 2000. *Commission Decision of 3 May 2000 replacing Decision 94/3/EC establishing a list of wastes pursuant to Article 1(a) of Council Directive 75/442/EEC on waste and Council Decision 94/904/EC establishing a list of hazardous waste pursuant to Article 1(4) of Council Directive 91/689/EEC on hazardous waste (notified under document number C(2000) 1147).*

EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT 2002. *Regulation (EC) No 2150/2002 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 November 2002 on Waste Statistics.*

EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT 2008. *Directive 2008/98/CE of the European Parliament and of the council of 19 November 2008 on waste and repealing certain Directives. Official Journal of the European Union.*

EUROSTAT 2010. *Guidance on classification of waste according to EWC-Stat categories. Supplement to the Manual for the Implementation of the Regulation (EC) No 2150/2002 on Waste Statistics. European Commission.*

EUROSTAT. 2017. *Eurostat statistics for waste flow generation 2014. European Commission [Online]. Available: <http://epp.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/portal/page/portal/eurostat/home/> [Accessed December 2017].*

FENTON, M. D. 2003. *Iron and steel recycling in the United States in 1998, US Department of the interior, US Geological survey.*

FIRSCHING, M., MUHLBAUER, J., MAURER, A., NACHTRAB, F. & UHLMANN, N. Year. *Quantitative sorting using dual energy X-ray transmission imaging. In: OCM 2013-optical characterization of materials—conference proceedings, 2013. 259-264.*

FISCHER, C., LEHNER, M. & MCKINNON, L. L. 2012. *Overview of the use of landfill taxes in Europe. ETC/SCP working paper 1/2012 European Topic Centre on Sustainable Consumption and Production.*

FROST & SULLIVAN 2011. *Strategic Analysis of the European Recycled Materials and Chemicals Market in Construction Industry.*

- GALLIVAN, V. 2018. *Asphalt Pavement Consulting. Material Recycling and Reuse Consultant* [Online]. United States. Available: <http://www.gallivanconsultinginc.com/> [Accessed January 2018].
- GANJIAN, E., POUYA, H. S., CLAISSE, P., WADDELL, M., HEMMING, S. & JOHANSSON, S. 2008. *Plasterboard and gypsum waste in a novel cementitious binder for road construction. Concrete Society London, 42, 20.*
- GESING, A. & HARBECK, H. Year. *Particle sorting of light-metal alloys and expanded use of manufacturing scrap in automotive, marine, and aerospace markets. In: Global symposium on recycling, waste treatment, and clean technology (REWAS), 2008.*
- GOUDSMIT MAGNETIC SYSTEMS. 2017. *Magnetic Separators for Recycling* [Online]. The Netherlands. Available: http://www.goudsmitmagnets.com/data/repository/documents/Brochure_Recycling_EN.pdf [Accessed December 2017].
- GRZEGORZEK, M., SCHWERBEL, D., BALTHASAR, D. & PAULUS, D. Year. *Automatic sorting of aluminium alloys based on spectroscopy measures. In: ÖAGM/AAPR Workshop, 2011.*
- GTOG PROJECT. 2013. *Life+ Gypsum to Gypsum (GtoG) project: From Production to Recycling, a Circular Economy for the European Gypsum Industry with the Demolition and Recycling Industry* [Online]. Available: <http://gypsumtogypsum.org/> [Accessed January 2018].
- GTOG PROJECT 2015. *DB4: Report on Production Process Parameters. GtoG project LIFE11 ENV/BE/001039.*
- GUNDUPALLI, S. P., HAIT, S. & THAKUR, A. 2017. *A review on automated sorting of source-separated municipal solid waste for recycling. Waste Management, 60, 56-74.*
- GYPNUM RECYCLING INTERNATIONAL. 2001. *Recycling unit* [Online]. Available: http://www.gypsumrecycling.biz/15897-1_Recyclingunit/ [Accessed January 2018].
- GYPNUM RECYCLING INTERNATIONAL. 2005. *Mobile Plasterboard Recycling Unit. Fact sheet: XL Model* [Online]. Denmark. Available: http://cmslogin.dk/Customers/Gypsum%20Recycling%20Int/Archive/747/GRU%20XL%20faktablad%202014_En.pdf [Accessed January 2018].
- HADŽIKADIĆ, M. & AVDAKOVIĆ, S. 2017. *Advanced Technologies, Systems, and Applications, Springer.*
- HELSEN, L. & VAN DEN BULCK, E. 2005. *Review of disposal technologies for chromated copper arsenate (CCA) treated wood waste, with detailed analyses of thermochemical conversion processes. Environmental Pollution, 134, 301-314.*

- HIETE, M. 2013. *Waste management plants and technology for recycling construction and demolition (C&D) waste: state-of-the-art and future challenges*. Handbook of Recycled Concrete and Demolition Waste. Elsevier.
- HOGG, D., VERGUNST, T., ELLIOTT, T., ELLIOTT, L., CORBIN, M. & BALLINGER, A. 2015. *Further development of the European reference Model on Waste Generation and Management. Final Report*. Luxembourg: European Commission.
- HOLLSTEIN, F., CACHO, Í., ARNAIZ, S. & WOHLLEBE, M. Year. *Challenges in automatic sorting of construction and demolition waste by hyperspectral imaging*. In: SPIE Commercial+ Scientific Sensing and Imaging, 2016. International Society for Optics and Photonics, 98620J-98620J-10.
- HOLLSTEIN, F., WOHLLEBE, M., HERLING, M., CACHO, I. & ARNAIZ, S. 2017. *Sorting of construction and demolition waste by hyperspectral-imaging*.
- HUANG, J., PRETZ, T. & BIAN, Z. Year. *Intelligent solid waste processing using optical sensor based sorting technology*. In: Image and Signal Processing (CISP), 2010 3rd International Congress on, 2010. IEEE, 1657-1661.
- HUBBE, M. A. 2014. *What next for wood construction/demolition debris?* BioResources, 10, 6-9.
- HUYSMAN, S., DEBAVEYE, S., SCHAUBROECK, T., DE MEESTER, S., ARDENTE, F., MATHIEUX, F. & DEWULF, J. 2015. *The recyclability benefit rate of closed-loop and open-loop systems: A case study on plastic recycling in Flanders*. Resources, Conservation and Recycling, 101, 53-60.
- IÇELLI, O., ERZENEÖĞLU, S. & BONCUKÇUOĞLU, R. 2003. *Measurement of mass attenuation coefficients of some boron compounds and the trommel sieve waste in the energy range 15.746–40.930 keV*. Journal of Quantitative Spectroscopy and Radiative Transfer, 78, 203-210.
- IRCOW PROJECT 2014. *Innovative Strategies for High-Grade Material Recovery from Construction and Demolition Waste. Final Summary Brochure*. Spain: Tecnalia Research & Innovation - Construction Unit.
- ISCARO, A. O. 2015. Gy.Eco - Gyproc Eco-friendly LIFE10 ENV/IT/000356 [Online]. Available: http://ec.europa.eu/environment/life/project/Projects/index.cfm?fuseaction=search.ds_pPage&n_proj_id=3938&docType=pdf [Accessed December 2017].
- JAPAN EXTERNAL TRADE ORGANIZATION 2013. *Environmental Technologies in Japan. Survey Reports on wastes treatment and recycling (FY 2012)*. In: ORGANIZATION, J. E. T. (ed.). Japan: Japan External Trade Organization.
- JEFFREY, C. 2011. *Construction and demolition waste recycling: A literature review*. Dalhousie University's Office of Sustainability, 35.

- JIMÉNEZ, J., AYUSO, J., LÓPEZ, M., FERNÁNDEZ, J. & DE BRITO, J. 2013. Use of fine recycled aggregates from ceramic waste in masonry mortar manufacturing. *Construction and Building Materials*, 40, 679-690.
- JUSTICE AND ENVIRONMENT 2012. *Implementation of the Waste Framework Directive in the EU Member States*. Brno: European Network of Environmental Law Organizations.
- KARA, P., ANTHONISSEN, J., MARGARITIS, A., JACOBS, G. & COUSCHEIR, K. Year. Recommendations and strategies for using reclaimed asphalt pavement in the Flemish Region based on a first life cycle assessment research. In: *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, 2017. IOP Publishing, 012088.
- KARLSSON, R. & ISACSSON, U. 2006. Material-related aspects of asphalt recycling—state-of-the-art. *Journal of Materials in Civil Engineering*, 18, 81-92.
- KOSTAS, E. T., BENEROSO, D. & ROBINSON, J. P. 2017. The application of microwave heating in bioenergy: A review on the microwave pre-treatment and upgrading technologies for biomass. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 77, 12-27.
- KULATUNGA, U., AMARATUNGA, D., HAIGH, R. & RAMEEZDEEN, R. 2006. Attitudes and perceptions of construction workforce on construction waste in Sri Lanka. *Management of Environmental Quality: An International Journal*, 17, 57-72.
- LEBLANC, R. 2016. An Overview of the shredder and its uses [Online]. Available: <https://www.thebalance.com/an-overview-of-the-shredder-and-its-uses-2877771> [Accessed December 2017].
- LEDESMA, E. F., JIMÉNEZ, J. R., AYUSO, J., FERNÁNDEZ, J. M. & DE BRITO, J. 2015. Maximum feasible use of recycled sand from construction and demolition waste for eco-mortar production—Part-I: ceramic masonry waste. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 87, 692-706.
- LEONELLI, C., VERONESI, P., BOCCACCINI, D., RIVASI, M., BARBIERI, L., ANDREOLA, F., LANCELLOTTI, I., RABITTI, D. & PELLACANI, G. 2006. Microwave thermal inertisation of asbestos containing waste and its recycling in traditional ceramics. *Journal of hazardous materials*, 135, 149-155.
- LIFE CERAM PROJECT 2016. *LIFE CERAM - Zero waste in ceramic tile manufacture. Final Report*. LIFE12 ENV/ES/000230. LIFE+ Project.
- LIPPIATT, N. & BOURGEOIS, F. 2012. Investigation of microwave-assisted concrete recycling using single-particle testing. *Minerals Engineering*, 31, 71-81.
- LISBONA, A. Year. Strategies for the recovery and recycling of raw materials from CDW: IRCOW and HISER projects. In: ACTION, M. C., ed. *Workshop "Recovery technologies for construction and demolition waste"* 16-17 November 2016 2016 Vienna.
- LONG, W. J. 1978. Gypsum wallboard-making process and product. *Composites*, 9, 133.

- MITSUBISHI MATERIALS. 2017. *Environment and recycle technology. Products and services* [Online]. Available: <http://www.mmc.co.jp/corporate/en/product/environment.html> [Accessed January 2018].
- MLINAR, C. Year. *Wet-screening plant. Onsite CDW and soil treatment*. In: ACTION, M. C., ed. *Workshop "Recovery technologies for construction and demolition waste"*, 2016 Vienna.
- MONIER, V., MUDGAL, S., HESTIN, M., TRARIEUX, M. & MIMID, S. 2011. *Service Contract on Management of Construction and Demolition Waste– Final Report Task 2. A project under the Framework contract*
- ENV.G.4/FRA/2008/0112. Brussels: European Commission DG ENV.
- MORALES CONDE, M. J., RODRÍGUEZ LIÑÁN, C. & PEDREÑO ROJAS, M. A. 2016. *Physical and mechanical properties of wood-gypsum composites from demolition material in rehabilitation works*. *Construction and Building Materials*, 114, 6-14.
- MORICONI, G., CORINALDESI, V. & ANTONUCCI, R. 2003. *Environmentally-friendly mortars: a way to improve bond between mortar and brick*. *Materials and Structures*, 36, 702-708.
- MOUSAVI, M., VENTURA, A., ANTHEAUME, N. & KIESSE, T. S. 2016. *LCA modelling of cement concrete waste management*.
- MTIBAA, R. Year. *Improving the recovery of construction and demolition waste. DEMOCLES Project*. In: ACTION, M. C., ed. *Workshop "Recovery technologies for construction and demolition waste" 16-17 November 2016 2016 Vienna*.
- MULDER, E., FEENSTRA, L. & DE JONG, T. Year. *Closed Cycle Construction–A process for the separation and reuse of the total C&D waste stream*. In: *International Conference on Sustainable Construction Materials and Technologies*, S, 2007. 27-34.
- NENO, C., BRITO, J. D. & VEIGA, R. 2014. *Using fine recycled concrete aggregate for mortar production*. *Materials research*, 17, 168-177.
- OLIVEIRA, J. R., SILVA, H. M., JESUS, C. M., ABREU, L. P. & FERNANDES, S. R. 2013. *Pushing the asphalt recycling technology to the limit*. *International Journal of Pavement Research and Technology*, 6, 109-116.
- OYENUGA, A., BHAMIDIARRI, R. & NAOUM, S. 2015. *Challenges in Managing Construction and Demolition Waste*. *Journal of Solid Waste Technology & Management*, 41.
- PETROVSZKI, K. Year. *Waste recycle software "zero waste goal"*. In: ACTION, M. C., ed. *Workshop "Recovery technologies for construction and demolition waste" 16-17 November 2016 2016 Vienna*.

- PHAROS PROJECT. *Why recycle gypsum waste?* [Online]. Available: <https://www.pharosproject.net/uploads/files/sources/1229/1372702389.pdf> [Accessed January 2018].
- PIGORSCH, E., GAERTNER, G., HOLLSTEIN, F. & MEINLSCHMIDT, P. 2014. Sorting of waste wood by NIR imaging techniques. *Proc. Sensor-Based Sorting*, 127-136.
- PLESCIA, P., GIZZI, D., BENEDETTI, S., CAMILUCCI, L., FANIZZA, C., DE SIMONE, P. & PAGLIETTI, F. 2003. Mechanochemical treatment to recycling asbestos-containing waste. *Waste Management*, 23, 209-218.
- PROCTOR, D., FEHLING, K., SHAY, E., WITTENBORN, J., GREEN, J., AVENT, C., BIGHAM, R., CONNOLLY, M., LEE, B. & SHEPKER, T. 2000. Physical and chemical characteristics of blast furnace, basic oxygen furnace, and electric arc furnace steel industry slags. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 34, 1576-1582.
- QUEREDA VÁZQUEZ, M., GARCÍA-TEN, F. J., ROS DOSDÁ, T., GIL ALBALAT, C., CHUMILLAS VILLALBA, D., ZAERA, V. & SEGURA MESTRE, M. 2016. *LIFECERAM. Residuo cero en la fabricación de baldosas cerámicas (Zero-waste in the manufacture of ceramic tiles)* Qualicer.
- RAHMAN, M., HUSSAIN, A. & BASRI, H. 2014. A critical review on waste paper sorting techniques. *International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology*, 11, 551-564.
- RAMACHANDRA, S. 2006. *Resource recovery and recycling from metallurgical wastes: Waste management series 7. The Netherlands: Elsevier BV.*
- RASMUSSEN, K. 2004. *Recycling apparatus for gypsum plasterboard. European Patent Application.*
- RAUTKOSKI, H., VÄHÄ-NISSI, M., KATAJA, K., GESTRANIUS, M., LIUKKONEN, S., MÄÄTTÄNEN, M., LIUKKONEN, J., KOUKO, J. & ASIKAINEN, S. 2016. Recycling of Contaminated Construction and Demolition Wood Waste. *Waste and Biomass Valorization*, 7, 615-624.
- REVOLVY. 2017. *Trommel screen* [Online]. Available: https://www.revolv.com/main/index.php?s=Trommel%20screen&item_type=topic [Accessed December 2017].
- RIGAMONTI, L. & PANTINI, S. Year. Construction and demolition waste management and recovery in Lombardy Region, Italy. In: ACTION, M. C., ed. *Workshop "Recovery technologies for construction and demolition waste" 16-17 November 2016 2016 Vienna.*
- RODRÍGUEZ-OREJÓN, A., DEL RÍO-MERINO, M. & FERNÁNDEZ-MARTÍNEZ, F. 2014. Characterization mixtures of thick gypsum with addition of treated waste from laminated plasterboards. *Materiales de Construcción*, 64, 018.

- SADAT-SHOJAI, M. & BAKHSHANDEH, G.-R. 2011. Recycling of PVC wastes. *Polymer Degradation and Stability*, 96, 404-415.
- SAIZ-MARTÍNEZ, P., GONZÁLEZ-CORTINA, M. & FERNÁNDEZ-MARTÍNEZ, F. 2015. Characterization and influence of fine recycled aggregates on masonry mortars properties. *Materiales de Construcción*, 65, 058.
- SENARATNE, S., LAMBROUSIS, G., MIRZA, O., TAM, V. W. & KANG, W.-H. 2017. Recycled Concrete in Structural Applications for Sustainable Construction Practices in Australia. *Procedia Engineering*, 180, 751-758.
- SIVILEVIČIUS, H., BRAŽIŪNAS, J. & PRENTKOVSKIS, O. 2017. Technologies and Principles of Hot Recycling and Investigation of Preheated Reclaimed Asphalt Pavement Batching Process in an Asphalt Mixing Plant. *Applied Sciences*, 7, 1104.
- STEINERT. 2017. Induction Sorting System ISS [Online]. STEINERT Elektromagnetbau GmbH. Available: [http://www.steinertglobal.com/fileadmin/user_upload/global/brochures/products_en/ISS - Induction_Sorter.pdf](http://www.steinertglobal.com/fileadmin/user_upload/global/brochures/products_en/ISS_-_Induction_Sorter.pdf) [Accessed December 2017].
- STROUP-GARDINER, M. 2011. Recycling and reclamation of asphalt pavements using in-place methods.
- TAM, V. W. Y. & TAM, C. M. 2006. A review on the viable technology for construction waste recycling. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 47, 209 - 221.
- TIMBERWOLF LTD. 2017. Professional green waste shredders. TW S426TDHB shredder [Online]. United Kingdom. Available: <https://www.timberwolf-uk.com/product-categories/professional-green-waste-shredders/> [Accessed December 2017].
- TOKYO MOKKOSHO. 2011. Recycling of Waste Wood and Waste Plastics into Recycled Plywood [Online]. Japan: Global Environment Centre Foundation. Available: http://nett21.gec.jp/Ecotowns/data/et_a-04.html [Accessed January 2018].
- TOUZÉ, S., BRU, K., MÉNARD, Y., WEH, A. & VON DER WEID, F. 2017. Electrical fragmentation applied to the recycling of concrete waste—Effect on aggregate liberation. *International Journal of Mineral Processing*, 158, 68-75.
- ULTRA SPREADER INTERNATIONAL. 2017. Ultra Trommel Screen [Online]. Ireland. Available: http://www.ultraspreader.com/products_screeners.php [Accessed December 2017].
- VEGAS, I., BROOS, K., NIELSEN, P., LAMBERTZ, O. & LISBONA, A. 2015. Upgrading the quality of mixed recycled aggregates from construction and demolition waste by using near-infrared sorting technology. *Construction and Building Materials*, 75, 121-128.

- VIANI, A. & GUALTIERI, A. F. 2013. *Recycling the product of thermal transformation of cement-asbestos for the preparation of calcium sulfoaluminate clinker*. *Journal of hazardous materials*, 260, 813-818.
- VOLKER WESSELS. 2013. *HERA System* [Online]. Rotterdam. Available: <https://en.volkerwessels.com/en/projects/detail/hera-system> [Accessed January 2018].
- VRANCKEN, C., LONGHURST, P. J. & WAGLAND, S. T. 2017. *Critical review of real-time methods for solid waste characterisation: Informing material recovery and fuel production*. *Waste Management*.
- WANG, C.-Q., WANG, H., FU, J.-G. & LIU, Y.-N. 2015. *Flotation separation of waste plastics for recycling—A review*. *Waste Management*, 41, 28-38.
- WANG, L., CHEN, S. S., TSANG, D. C., POON, C.-S. & SHIH, K. 2016. *Recycling contaminated wood into eco-friendly particleboard using green cement and carbon dioxide curing*. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 137, 861-870.
- WASTECARE CORPORATION. 2017. *Industrial shredders, grinders and shredder systems* [Online]. United States. Available: https://www.wastecare.com/Articles/Shredders_Grinders.htm [Accessed December 2017].
- WATSON, D. E. 2011. *Literature review of hot in-place recycling. Final Report*. Alabama, USA: Florida Department of Transportation and National Center for Asphalt Technology.
- WHEELER, P. A. & ROME, L. 2002. *Waste Pre-Treatment: A Review*. R&D Technical Report PI-344/TR. In: AGENCY, E. (ed.). United Kingdom: AEA Technology Environment.
- WIRTGEN. 2017. *Large milling machine W 210 / W 210i. Versatile front loader for professional operations* [Online]. Available: <https://www.wirtgen.de/en/products/cold-milling-machines/large-milling-machines/w210w210iw.php> [Accessed January 2018].
- WORLD HEALTH ORGANIZATION 2000. *Air quality guidelines for Europe*. Chapter 6.2 *Asbestos*, World Health Organization,.
- WORLD STEEL ASSOCIATION 2011. *Life Cycle assessment methodology report*. Brussels, Belgium: World Steel Association.
- WRAP 2002. *Plasterboard Case Study. International practice in plasterboard recycling: Denmark*. Gypsum Recycling International A/S. The Waste & Resources Action Programme.
- WRAP 2012. *PAS 111:2012. Specification for the requirements and test methods for processing waste wood*. United Kingdom: British Standard Institution.

WRAP & WSP ENVIRONMENTAL LIMITED 2009. *Collection Techniques for Construction, Demolition and Excavation Wastes. Final Report. United Kingdom: WRAP.*

WRING PROJECT. 2016. *Wood working industry recycling project [Online]. Available: <https://www.cdeglobal.com/media/4570/fees-candy-project-quarry-management-en.pdf> [Accessed January 2018].*

WU, G., LI, J. & XU, Z. 2013. *Triboelectrostatic separation for granular plastic waste recycling: A review. Waste Management, 33, 585-597.*

ZAUMANIS, M., MALLICK, R. B. & FRANK, R. 2014. *100% recycled hot mix asphalt: A review and analysis. Resources, Conservation and Recycling, 92, 230-245.*

ZAUMANIS, M., MALLICK, R. B. & FRANK, R. 2016. *100% hot mix asphalt recycling: challenges and benefits. Transportation Research Procedia, 14, 3493-3502.*

ZEN ROBOTICS. 2016. *Automated robotic sorting [Online]. Available: <http://zenrobotics.com/solutions/robotic-waste-sorting/> [Accessed December 2017].*